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Health, demographic change and wellbeing

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The health potential of urban water: future outlooks on local opportunities; *BlueHealth* scenarios for Amsterdam, Barcelona, Plymouth, Tallinn and Thessaloniki

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BlueHealth aimed to understand the relationships between exposure to blue space and human health and well-being. The public health impacts of changes to both natural blue spaces and associated urban infrastructure in Europe were investigated using a transdisciplinary approach (www.bluehealth2020.eu).

Information use for the development of these trends and ambitions was collected during stakeholder workshops attended by local experts and stakeholders in Amsterdam (May 15th, 2017), Plymouth (December 12th, 2018), Barcelona (March 13th, 2019), Tallinn (April 16th, 2019) and Thessaloniki (September 19th, 2019)) and from publicly available documents.

The images in this report are visualized quotes of the participants and were made during these workshops.

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1 Introduction

Although cities can be characterised as sources of economic, environmental and social challenges, they can also be part of the solution for healthy and sustainable societies. While most cities are situated close to water, whether inland waterways, lakes, or the sea, these blue spaces are not integrated into urban planning to their full potential and their public health impacts are not always recognised by planning authorities. Furthermore, cities face future challenges regarding climate change, economic developments like tourism, urbanisation, and rising social inequalities. The development of healthy blue spaces can support cities in their pursuit of ways to confront these challenges.

Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary analyses of the local impacts of these trends and promising interventions have been scarce to date. The BlueHealth project has explored the use of such methodology by presenting experiences related to five European cities: Amsterdam, Barcelona, Plymouth, Tallinn and Thessaloniki, using an interactive and participative approach with local experts and stakeholders (Wuijts, De Vries et al. under review). This report encompasses the future outlooks or scenarios that have been developed for each of these cities. The scenarios are based on the question: what contributory role could healthy blue spaces play in enhancing the impacts of long term trends? The results highlight the importance of addressing the local context when seeking sustainable solutions for cities. The future outlooks deliver information that could serve as useful input for local planning processes.

2 Protocol for developing local BlueHealth scenarios

This chapter describes the basic steps towards creating BlueHealth future outlooks or scenarios. In the BlueHealth Trend report (Wuijts, De Vries et al. 2019) report a more elaborate description of trends and the scenario methodology can be found. Materials for BlueHealth local workshops and scenarios are based upon the more general trends described in the BlueHealth Trend report (Wuijts, De Vries et al. 2019). A full description of the methodology can be found in (Wuijts, De Vries et al. under review).

The development of BlueHealth scenarios has been divided into three consequent steps:

1. Preparation:
 - a. Collecting general information on the current situation of the concerning city / region including all DESTEP-sectors (Demography, Economy, Social-cultural, Technology, Ecology/Environment, Politics/Institutions). This was the input for a poster that summarizes some of the relevant characteristics and issues that affect water and health issues in this specific place and that was used during the stakeholder workshop (Step 2) to provide all participants the same on background information of the city, since participants have different backgrounds.
 - b. Preparing poster material for workshop.

2. Organisation of a local stakeholder workshop:

- a. Preparation and organisation of the workshop together with local counterpart, since they have the knowledge and connections needed to better understand the local situation and issues.
- b. A broad range of stakeholders in health and water that are experts on the local situation regarding several aspects of BlueHealth have been invited to the workshops. Preferably their areas of expertise covered all DESTEP-sectors (Demography, Economy, Social-cultural, Technology, Ecology/Environment, Politics/Institutions).
- c. During the workshop the focus is on 1) Identifying local ambitions and values that influence the direction of policy making; 2) Identifying relevant trends for the local situation and discussing their impacts for the future; 3) Identifying possible interventions for policy action. Poster templates for these activities and discussions are available.

3. Drafting the local scenarios:

The scenarios have been fed by the input from the stakeholder workshop and relevant policy plans and documents.

- a. Values identified during the workshop were used as ambitions for the local future outlooks.
- b. Trends identified as relevant were connected to the ambitions mentioned.
- c. Selected ambitions and trends were consequently tested and supplemented with information from policy documents and, if available, projection data. Existing data, maps and policy examples were used to illustrate and enrich the scenario report. Challenges and opportunities could thus be identified.
- d. Interventions that were identified during the workshop were included, thus creating a first step towards pathways that need to be set out in order to achieve the ambitions formulated and thus provide input to local planning processes.
- e. Feedback from workshop attendees was included in the scenario development at two stages: on the workshop outcomes (input for the scenarios) and the draft scenarios.

3 BlueHealth Futures: Trends and ambitions for Amsterdam

3.1 BlueHealth trends for Amsterdam

The Netherlands, a country in the North-Western part of Europe, are characterized by its high population density, high economic activity, moderate sea climate and its situation in the delta of four major international river basins (Rhine, Meuse, Scheldt and Ems). Fifty-nine per cent of the country, including the 3rd largest European metropolitan area and almost half of the Dutch population, lies below sea level.

Amsterdam, the capital of the Netherlands, is a relative densely populated urban area (854,000 citizens in 2018 and 1,003,000 expected in 2040 (5,042 inhabitants/km²)), including a port complex and adjacent industrial zones with high economic value and high vulnerability to flooding. The city has been built around the rivers Rhine and Amstel in the twelfth century and situated below sea level. Due to climate change, the risk of flooding will increase in the future, especially as a result of heavy rainfall in the city itself. The risks of sea level rise is expected to be of a lesser concern due to the high level protection by dykes in the Netherlands.

BlueHealth trends for Amsterdam in 2040

What developments will Amsterdam be facing in the coming decades when it comes to its urban waters and its potential to affect public health and well-being? What are relevant trends if we project current developments to the future?

During an interactive, multidisciplinary stakeholder workshop on May 15th, 2017 in Amsterdam, with experts and local professionals with backgrounds in water quality management, public health, spatial planning, policy and governance, social science, technology, climate, and environment, six trends related to these questions, have been identified as dominant for Amsterdam. For this assessment, a longlist of trends was analysed, which was assembled using the DESTEP (demography, economy, social-cultural, technology, ecology and climate, political-institutional) methodology (RIVM 2014). In this trend scenario, we focus upon these six trends, that have been clustered around three central themes.

1. *How will climate change and water availability influence life in Amsterdam? (ecology and climate):*
 - More fluctuation in water availability and an increasing water scarcity;
 - Increased risk of urban flooding primarily due to heavy rainfall;
2. *How will social inequalities develop? (social-cultural):*
 - Rising inequalities;
 - Social cohesion will be increasingly under pressure, in particular due to further individualism (e.g., resulting in loneliness);
3. *What are political-institutional developments in the field of water and health? (political-institutional):*
 - Decision-making is moving from (central) government to multi-actor (network) governance;
 - Multi-sectoral approaches in spatial planning and wider public engagement.

Description of trends for Amsterdam

1. *How will climate change and water availability influence life in Amsterdam?*

The effects of climate change will become significant towards the end of the 21st century and thus beyond the timescale of the Trendscenario (2040) (Rajczak and Schär 2017). Even so, extreme weather events (heavy rainfall, heat waves and drought) will occur more frequently in the coming decades in Europe (Cann, Thomas et al. 2013, IPCC 2014, KNMI 2014, Forzieri, Cescatti et al. 2017) and Amsterdam (<http://klimaatverandering-mra.vormgeving.com>). Effects beyond 2040 need to be counted for in long term urban planning. These events will affect water availability, water quality and public health (Delpha, Jung et al. 2009, Whitehead, Wilby et al. 2009, EEA 2017). The public health effects include increased heat stress, respiratory complaints and exposure to waterborne and vectorborne pathogens

and may be exacerbated, especially in urban areas, if no or limited adaptation measures are implemented (Kleerekoper et al., 2012; EEA, 2017; Wuijts et al., 2014, Scoccimarro et al., 2017). Figure 3.1 shows the projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) for the Amsterdam region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005, based on EURO-CORDEX modeling (see Annex II).

Figure 3.1 Projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) in the Amsterdam region (see Annex II) compared to the timeframe 1986-2005.

Heavy rainfall

High precipitation events mainly occur in summer months (KNMI 2014). The spatial scale of flooding by heavy rainfall ranges from street-level in case of short summer storms to regional in case of more prolonged high intensity storms. The risk of sewage overflow is expected to rise if no adaptation measures are implemented. Furthermore, temporary storage of rainwater at the streets will occur more often as the sewage system is not able to process all the rainwater. Therefore, the city of Amsterdam is working on a programme to increase the capacity of the sewage system to 60 mm per hour (expected rainfall frequency of 100 years). In “Amsterdam Rainproof” the impact of heavy rainfall (120 mm in 2 hours) has been calculated for the city. Areas with excess water have been compared to vital functions such as hospitals, musea and major transportation routes (see Figure 3.2). The resulting effects from water quality changes on health, have not yet been included.

Figure 3.2 Bottlenecks in Amsterdam in case of heavy rainfall (https://www.rainproof.nl/sites/default/files/regenwaterkelpuntenkaart_amsterdam.pdf).

In case of overflow, untreated sewage water is being discharged to the urban surface water, including pathogenic microorganisms, chemicals and pharmaceutical residues (Sterk, De Man et al. 2016, Schmitt, Blaak et al. 2017). Alternatively, such organisms originate from surrounding soils by runoff (Schalk, Docters van Leeuwen et al. 2012, De Man, Mughini Gras et al. 2016). If people are exposed to contaminated urban water, they might become infected by pathogens (De Man, Van den Berg et al. 2014). Other health effects caused by (local) flooding due to climate change include mental health problems (e.g. safety concerns) or risks of drowning (Hames and Vardoulakis 2012). The latter is particularly relevant for children, people with a migration background, and tourists, since the ability to swim among these groups is lower than on average in the Netherlands (Garsen, Hoogenboezem et al. 2008).

Heat stress

It is expected that not only the average temperature and perceived temperature will rise, but also the number of very warm days (from 21 days with temperatures over 25 °C to over 30 days in 2050 in the Netherlands) (KNMI 2014) (see also Figure 3.1). This rise is even more pronounced when focusing upon extreme events (Soccimarro, Fogli et al. 2017). In addition, following higher air temperatures, water temperatures may rise, leading to growth of pathogenic microorganisms (Sterk, Schets et al. 2015). In case warm days coincide with rainfall higher incidences of legionellosis are observed (Beauté, Sandin et al. 2016). In urban areas, the daily and nocturnal temperatures may be even higher. This ‘urban heat

island effect' is partly due to the limited potential of urban areas to cool down during the night. Due to this urban heat island effect, temperatures in the city centre of Amsterdam can be up to 10 °C higher than in its outskirts on a sunny day (Van der Hoeven and Wandl 2013) (https://www.atlasleefomgeving.nl/kaarten?config=alo_kijken_10681&layers=cd17b155-7cc1-3ea3-b54b-b6e4bb399689,1,0.8,0;&x=120476&y=486703&zoom=9&rotation=0&baselayer=992). Heat stress may result in an increase of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases and especially affect the elderly, young children and chronically ill people. Due to ageing, is the proportion of the elderly (> 65 years) expected to rise in Amsterdam from 12 % (2018) to 17 % (2040) (see Figure 3.3) (Municipality of Amsterdam 2018). The number of young children is expected to remain relatively stable. As a result, the number of citizens potentially affected by heat stress, increases by almost 70,000.

The increase of the average temperature and perceived temperature may also lead to an increased need of citizens for cooling places and activities, such as swimming in canals and ponds, water playgrounds etcetera.

Figure 3.3 Demography of Amsterdam towards 2040 (number of citizens), identified for different age groups (Municipality of Amsterdam 2018).

Drought

The amount of fresh water available is influenced by climate change, urbanisation, population growth, and economic trends (e.g., agricultural innovation). Climate change leads to major changes in water availability across Europe. On the scale of Amsterdam, water scarcity is not considered to be an issue, although water quality issues may increase due to low water flows in the urban water system (ref) with consequences for bathing water quality.

2. *How will social inequalities develop?*

Social cohesion will be increasingly under pressure in the coming decades, due to growing individualism and increasing social inequalities, leading to more polarization and segregation. Income inequality will continue to rise (see Figure 3.4).

Individualisation can be a driver for technological innovations and improvements in cultural, economic and political organisation. On the other hand, individualisation brings about uncertainties and controversies that are able to increase tensions and conflicts in Europe and within European countries (Genov, 2014). Increasing individualisation can “undermine solidarity as the social glue of life” (Genov, 2014, p. 3), and have negative impact on the quality of life of people. This is how individualism can lead to social exclusion and increasing inequalities, leaving part of society behind in the benefits that are brought about through technological, economic and political development and others deprived of these benefits. This has an impact on people’s well-being. Part of society will be able to care for itself and enjoy the possibilities of making own choices when it comes to healthcare and well-being. Others will need more support from their surroundings and the welfare state, especially vulnerable and elderly people. Elderly and people with chronicle illnesses are more vulnerable to the consequences of heatwaves. The combination with social exclusion could worsen the health consequences of these types of events, due to missing information or care.

Figure 3.4 Income differences in Amsterdam (low to high = yellow to red) (PBL 2015).

Higher inequity in society is correlated with greater social unrest. Access to blue space may be better for high income groups (e.g. higher property values when properties face water (Luttik, 2000)). In general, income inequality may have a negative effect on environmental quality (e.g. Camilo Cardenas et al., 2002; Drabo, 2011). Differences between different neighborhoods will become more pronounced. Centrally located districts often are upgraded by an influx of more affluent residents resulting in higher quality of living but also increasing home prices. This process is referred to as gentrification. Simultaneously, lower income households are forced to move to neighborhoods with

lower housing costs. These neighborhoods are often characterized by a clustering of other unfavorable factors as well, such as higher crime rates and low environmental quality. In Amsterdam, gentrification can be identified e.g. alongside the Amstel river banks and within the city ring where housing prices are rising very fast, thus strongly limiting housing options for low and middle incomes.

3. *What are political-institutional developments in the field of water and health?*

In the coming decades citizens express their views on their outdoor environment more explicitly, take a more critical stand towards their governments and want to be part of the decision making process. This development can be recognised both at an EU and at a national level, although there are differences between Member States (Staatsen, Van der Vliet et al. 2017). Complex environmental issues and multiple societal interests challenge authorities to develop cross-sectoral and multi-disciplinary approaches, for instance in the case of climate adaptation. Perspectives on effectiveness of these approaches may be different for different sectors. This sets a challenge to authorities to manage these expectations and their interactions to other objectives.

In the Netherlands, a shift has taken place in how roles and responsibilities are assigned to (other) governmental bodies for different functions related to water and public health due to decentralization and deregulation by the national government. Amsterdam has taken a frontrunner position in this development. The role of both the municipality and the water company in realizing the water quality objectives of the Water Framework Directive and the Bathing Directive will increase.

The adaptation and mitigation needs that come from climate change create a sense of urgency towards interventions in water infrastructure related to energy supply (e.g. biogas, geothermal energy, energy from surface water), flooding and heat stress prevention. The municipality of Amsterdam has set out a strategy to combine new initiatives with flood resilience measures. City planners and project developers use criteria for sustainable design. Attention is increasing for criteria for a healthy environment (including water quality) among city planners. This can be attributed to both citizen's wishes and concerns and regulations.

3.2 BlueHealth ambitions for Amsterdam in 2040

On the 15th of May, 2017 experts and local professionals with backgrounds in water quality management, public health, spatial planning, policy and governance, social science, technology, climate, and environment met for a workshop on future perspectives for BlueHealth in Amsterdam. During the workshop, two values were identified as dominant for Amsterdam: climate resilience and promoting social equity. These values have been used as the basis for normative views on Amsterdam in 2040. The information from the trendscenario was used to identify challenges and opportunities that might be met when realizing these views. Input on interventions was abstracted from the discussion during the workshop.

3.2.1 'Climate-resilience for a healthy Amsterdam'

Desired future

The City of Amsterdam is climate resilient in 2040 according to ambitions laid down in the Water Vision Amsterdam 2040 (https://issuu.com/gemeenteamsterdam/docs/watervisie_amsterdam_2040). The municipality has anticipated adequately on increasing risks of heat stress and increasing risks of

flooding from heavy rainfall and attributed health effects. Adaptation to climate change has been used as a window of opportunity to develop healthy living environments in the city of Amsterdam, thereby promoting the quality of life and the spatial attractiveness of its canals and waters, for both citizens and companies, and removing possible new health risks from climate adaptation such as waterborne diseases and injuries.

Challenges and opportunities on the way to climate resilience

Challenges:

- The effects of climate change will become significant towards the end of the 21st century and thus beyond the timescale of this scenario (2040) (Rajczak and Schär 2017). Even so, extreme weather events (heavy rainfall, especially during winter, heat waves and drought) will occur more frequently in the coming decades in the Amsterdam region (KNMI 2014, Rajczak and Schär 2017).
- Climate resilience calls for measures to adapt for water excess and water shortages, and related issues towards water quality. In case of extreme rainfall, excess water on the streets cannot be discharged by the sewage system and overflows pollute canals and other surface water with untreated sewage water. Due to the long lifetimes of urban infrastructure, effects beyond 2040 need to be counted for in long term urban planning as well.
- Long periods of high temperatures and drought may lead to algae blooms and the development of water quality problems due to the low base flow in the water system and ongoing inputs from various activities.
- Investments in good quality of canals and surface waters attribute to the attractiveness of the city to live in, but could also attribute to more gentrification and widen the social gap.

- Spatial interventions like water squares have to compete with other interests. The adagium 'Not in my backyard' is challenging climate adaptation interventions.
- There is little awareness among citizens on the risks of swimming in urban water (infectious diseases, drowning, injuries).

Opportunities:

- Realisation of storage capacity of excess water may offer opportunities to realise water play grounds.
- Investments in sewage capacity offers a momentum to redesign the use of overflows in the sewage collection system.

- Due to temperature rise, there is an increasing need from citizens, for cooling spaces and cooling activities, such as swimming or water play grounds.
- Availability of attractive and good quality waters as well as facilities to access the water and be protected from other functions like shipping, encourages people of all ages to recreate and swim.

Interventions contributing to resilience and health

Interventions in multiple policy domains, e.g. related to work, income, housing, transport, can affect climate resilience and health directly or indirectly. Especially in urban environments with a high density of activities and usages of space and complex social interactions. Within this future scenario for Amsterdam we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to the realisation of climate resilience and health. Instruments to adapt the outdoor environment to the effects of climate change in ways that are beneficial to health generally include interventions in blue and green spaces, like water playgrounds, wadis, water squares, and parks. Other types of interventions might focus on awareness raising among citizens and companies, effectiveness of governance arrangements and robust and healthy urban design.

Legal instruments

The upcoming Dutch Environmental and Planning Act (to be implemented by 2021) entails a specific objective regarding a healthy environment. The act will give municipalities the opportunity to explicitly involve citizens in an early phase of rural and urban planning. Climate change adaptation, health

protection, and health promotion will be part of the municipal environmental visions (<https://aandeslagmetdeomgevingswet.nl/thema/gezonde-fysieke/>).

In the National Delta Decision on Spatial Adaptation authorities (national government, provinces, municipalities and water authorities) have set down the joint ambition to have the Netherlands as climate-proof and water-resilient as possible by 2050. By 2020, all these parties will have incorporated climate-proof and water-resilient planning into their policies and actions, by analysing their local challenges, translating these challenges into an ambition and adaptation strategy to achieve this ambition (<https://ruimtelijkeadaptatie.nl/english/delta-decision/delta-decision/>).

Both developments offer opportunities to create healthy blue spaces for Amsterdam's citizens to benefit from.

The presence of good quality bathing locations invites people to relax, interact and also to exercise. This has a positive effect on a healthy lifestyle.

Future planning of bathing and recreation

To enable future bathing and recreation in urban spaces, reservations for swimming facilities have to be made in environmental and spatial plans as well as the development of targeted strategies for water quality improvement. A wider focus on the other districts in the city, next to the city centre, would enhance the ambitions of 'water for all' of the Amsterdam Water Vision.

A common policy brief for wild swimming may reduce accidents and health incidents by means of communication and enforcement.

Health check in resilient urban design

Use or create blue spaces to increase storage capacity during heavy rainfall, but include health aspects in design and operation to avoid microbiological contamination. The adaptive multi-layer safety approach as has been developed in Amsterdam in 2013 to anticipate on the increased risk of flooding (prevention, sustainable spatial design, crisis management) can be combined with the ambitions on a healthy outdoor environment, to decrease potential risks and get health benefits from new projects. For this purpose, the adaptive approach has to be complemented with health based criteria (e.g. (Schets, De Man et al. 2017). City planners and project developers use these criteria to test applications for new spatial initiatives. Examples of blue or green spaces: (<https://www.urbangreenbluegrids.com/design-tool/>, <http://www.hva.nl/praktisch/algemeen/etalage/de-stad/de-stad.html>)

Incentives to stimulate private initiatives

Municipalities could work towards 'healthy habitats' that nudge a healthy lifestyle, in which people are part of society, self-reliant and empowered and that take possible environmental health and infection risks into account. Positive incentives (financial or other) can be used to stimulate initiatives by citizens and companies to increase the healthy adaptive capacity of the city.

Awareness raising

Currently, Amsterdam has multiple locations where people go for a swim, also within the city centre, not all of them officially registered as an official bathing water location. Wild swim initiatives may cause risks on injuries and water quality related health issues. Citizens are often unaware of the risks and

their own responsibilities. Communication and engagement practices (e.g. by citizen science on bathing water quality) can be used to increase awareness on health risks and benefits.

Monitoring and communication

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and develop an adaptation strategy in case measures do not lead to the expected result.

3.2.2 'A healthy city for all: Our Amsterdam'

Desired future

In 2040, Amsterdam is a fully inclusive city. People feel at home, nobody is left behind. People with various (cultural or ethnic) backgrounds and those whom experience activity limitations or suffer from chronic conditions are able to enjoy the city and make use of the opportunities that Amsterdam offers. Public (blue and green) spaces are safe, and available and accessible for all population groups, also in (previously) deprived neighbourhoods (https://issuu.com/gemeenteamsterdam/docs/watervisie_amsterdam_2040).

Challenges and opportunities on the way to inclusiveness

Challenges:

- Climate change, with higher temperatures and higher risks of flooding, puts pressure on the safety of blue spaces. This could result in a higher risk of waterborne diseases. Areas prone to flooding might be in parts already more deprived neighbourhoods in the city (see Figures 3.2 and 3.4 in trends scenario).
- The population of Amsterdam is growing, mainly due to migration (national and international). The population growth in combination with smaller household sizes will increase the demand for housing and infrastructure. This might put a higher pressure on available blue and green spaces.
- Due to international migration, ethnic diversity will increase. In 2040, 70% of the population has a mixed ethnic background. This results also in a diversity of needs and demands of the services that blue spaces can provide. We know that people with a migration background and elderly make more use of parks in the city. This might also be the case for blue spaces.
- With a growing ethnic and language diversity, it might also be more difficult to reach all population groups with relevant information about the possibilities of how to use blue spaces, but also about the risks of using and being in blue spaces. For example regarding the danger of injuries, drowning or contamination.

- Income inequalities will rise. Together with increasing pressure on affordable housing this will result in a challenge to keep Amsterdam a place that is accessible for everyone. The scarcity of housing also leads to basements being used as apartments; these houses are more vulnerable in case of water calamities and flooding.
- The increasing role of the private sector in shaping the blue and green spaces might result in further commercialization of the services that these spaces can provide for the general public. Privatization of blue and green spaces could jeopardise the accessibility of these spaces and services for all. Changing institutional and governance structures, resulting in smaller (local) governmental budgets that cannot longer ensure universal access might enforce this development. This raises the question to what extent green/blue spaces are public or private goods.

Opportunities:

- Climate change adaptation measures could be used as an incentive to give certain less attractive areas opportunities to improve its outdoor spaces.
- Open water swimming places are a cheaper and accessible option for people to use than swimming pools. Especially in less favoured areas this could be helpful to have affordable and accessible blue spaces (e.g. Slotterplas). Swimming lessons in natural water could be used to reduce the risks of drowning and to increase awareness on other risks as well.
- Use of former industrial and harbour areas (e.g. Dutch Navy Area) for residential and recreational use.

- The coming Environment and Planning Act sets specific objectives regarding public health for local authorities and stakeholders. These objectives could be used as a vehicle to realise the objectives for inclusiveness.

Interventions contributing to access for all

Interventions in multiple policy domains, e.g. related to work, income, housing, transport, can affect climate resilience and health directly or indirectly. Especially in urban environments with a high density of activities and usages of space and complex social interactions. Within this future scenario for Amsterdam we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to the realization of access for all related to the topic of water and health. Interventions that contribute to inclusiveness have a focus on awareness raising, communication and engagement. These are also elements that are anchored in processes of urban planning, but are often only used by a limited group of citizens. To find ways to open up these options and engage other groups as well is a challenge for this ambition.

Spatial planning policy

A way to support the healthy use of blue spaces is to create more options for blue recreation by the allocation of more open water spaces.

Another aspect of spatial planning to think of is the redevelopment of (old industrial and derelict) waterfronts for new purposes such as recreation and housing that is accessible for different income and age groups. Furthermore, to safeguard to right to the city for all and maintaining an affordable living standard, it is important to mitigate for the negative impacts of tourism. For example by restricting the number of cruise ships and introducing stricter policies for renting out private homes through platforms such as Airbnb.

Awareness raising

Currently, Amsterdam has multiple locations where people go for a swim, also within the city centre. However, not all of these places are registered as an official bathing water location. Open water

swimming initiatives may cause risks on injuries and water quality related health issues. Citizens are often unaware of the risks and their own responsibilities. Communication and engagement practices (e.g. by citizen science on bathing water quality) can be used to increase awareness on health risks and benefits. It is important that these communication and engagement practices address different age groups, gender and cultural diverse groups in multi languages.

Monitoring and communication

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders, including citizens, increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and develop an adaptation strategy in case measures do not lead to the expected result.

Involvement of local community

Involvement of local community to get a better understanding of local needs, to use local knowledge on what works and what doesn't (local community process with combination of people that have a lot of knowledge and less knowledge) and to promote participation for decision making.

3.3 Wrap up BlueHealth Futures for Amsterdam

The impacts of climate change can affect the livelihood in Amsterdam in various ways. Heavy rainfall increases the risk of sewage overflow with direct risks for public health since untreated sewage water can be discharged to the urban surface water including pathogenic microorganisms, chemicals and pharmaceutical residues. This increases the risks of infectious diseases but also mental health could be affected because of safety concerns. In addition, increasing temperatures in combination with the urban heat island effect, partly caused by the limited potential of urban areas too cool during the night, may cause heat stress resulting in an increase of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases specially among the elderly, young children and chronically ill. Therefore, the demand for places near the water as place for cooling down will increase.

Income inequalities are expected to rise further and may result in an increase of social inequalities as well. The already ongoing gentrification of some neighborhoods in Amsterdam in turn may result in lesser accessibility to blue spaces for lower and middle incomes. Combined with the increased individualization, this may result in social exclusion and potentially have negative health consequences.

The trends described do not only present different challenges that need to be tackled, but opportunities as well. The availability of attractive and good quality blue spaces as well as facilities to access the water and to be protected from other functions like shipping, encourages people of all ages to recreate and swim and may help reduce individualization. To enable future bathing and recreation in urban spaces, swimming facilities have to be included in environmental and spatial plans as well as the development of targeted strategies for water quality improvement, which also can contribute to the reduction of the urban heat island effect.

Since local authorities are considered to be more suited to address local needs and wishes, a shift can be identified towards a more decentralized government with more power to local authorities. This

gives Amsterdam the opportunity to adapt and mitigate the effects of climate change in a pro-active way, and the possibility to combine new initiatives with flood resilient measures.

An integrated multisectoral governance approach tackling the aforementioned issues is desired to create these co-benefits, but one has to be wary of the unintended effects and trade-offs. Investments in good quality of canals and surface waters attribute to the attractiveness of the city to live in, but could also attract more people to Amsterdam and may enforce gentrification and widen social gaps. Although these are not mutually exclusive, choices need to be made as to what should be prioritized in order to have a climate resilient and healthy city for all.

4 BlueHealth Futures: Trends and ambitions for Barcelona

4.1 BlueHealth trends for Barcelona

Spain is a country in South Europe and is situated on the Iberian Peninsula (apart from two archipelagoes located in the Mediterranean Sea and Atlantic Ocean, and its African enclaves). Mainland Spain is bordered to the south and east by the Mediterranean Sea; to the north by the Bay of Biscay; and to the west and northwest by the Atlantic Ocean. Spain is a mountainous country but also has low altitude coastal zones that might be prone to coastal flooding (Government of Spain 2017).

Barcelona, the second most populous city in Spain, is situated in the north east and is the capital of the autonomous community of Catalonia. The city is one of the largest urban conurbations situated on the Mediterranean Sea, and is further bordered by the mouths of the rivers Llobregat and Besòs, and by the Serra de Collserola mountain range. The mountain and rivers act as natural borders between municipalities. The governance of these areas takes place at multiple levels (i.e. the Barcelona City Council and at the Metropolitan area level). The city has a very high population density (16,000 per km²), is characterized by its rich cultural heritage and is a major tourist destination, (>30 M tourist visitors per year in 2017). The city has a large port that consists of a commercial, logistics, and historical zone. There are a number of beaches along the south-eastern edge of the city. Barcelona has a Mediterranean climate with mild winters and warm-hot summers. Rainfall is infrequent and there can be long periods without rain. Droughts are a re-occurring concern. However, when it rains, it can be intense and the high volume of rainfall, the terrain, the largely impermeable surface and extensive canalization of rivers all contribute to flooding.

BlueHealth trends for Barcelona in 2040

What are relevant trends if we project current developments to the future? What developments will Barcelona be facing in the coming decades when it comes to its urban waters and its potential to affect public health and well-being?

Six trends related to these questions, have been assessed as most dominant for Barcelona, during an interactive, multidisciplinary stakeholder workshop on March 13th, 2019 in Barcelona, with experts and local professionals with backgrounds in water quality management, public health, spatial planning, architecture, policy and governance, social science, technology, climate, and environment,. For this assessment, a longlist of trends was used as an input (Wuijts, De Vries et al. 2019), which was assembled using the DESTEP (demography, economy, social-cultural, technology, ecology and climate, political-institutional) methodology (RIVM 2014). In the Trend scenario for Barcelona, we focus upon the five trends identified as most relevant, that cover five of the DESTEP categories:

1. *How will inequalities develop in Barcelona due to changes in income distribution?*
2. *How will climate change and water availability affect the livability of Barcelona?*
3. *How will political and institutional developments have an impact on decision-making within the domains of water and health in the city?*
4. *Will new water management technology create solutions for Barcelona's future water and climate challenges?*
5. *How will the city of Barcelona cope with an ageing population in the coming decades?*

Description of trends for Barcelona

1. How will income inequalities develop?

In the past decade income inequality levels have remained high. Across OECD countries, the average Gini coefficient of the distribution of the disposable household income reached 0.318 in 2013/2014, only marginally higher than in 2007, but the highest value on record since the mid-1980s (OECD 2017).

Given these numbers, it remains important for governments to take into account the inequalities related to access to water for all, as well as the quality thereof. In these future outlooks, we focus on water for recreation, not on drinking water or water for sanitation. The same goes for access to quality and affordable healthcare. In general, higher inequality in society is correlated with greater social unrest. Access to blue space may be better for high income groups (e.g. higher property values when properties face water (Luttik 2000)). In general, income inequality may have a negative effect on environmental quality (Camilo Cardenas, Stranlund et al. 2002, Drabo 2011).

The Gini coefficient for Barcelona City was 0.291 in 2017 (City of Barcelona 2017a), scoring lower than the Barcelona Metropolitan Area (0.325) and Spain as a whole (0.341 (INE 2017)) and lower than the

EU average (0.307 (Eurostat 2019)) in the same year, indicating less inequality in Barcelona City than in the larger Barcelona Metro Area. According to the City Council of Barcelona, there is a strong spatial concentration of poverty in certain neighbourhoods in Barcelona (City of Barcelona 2017b).

The City Council is committed to fighting poverty, especially in deprived neighbourhoods. One of the areas that is being focused on is Eix Besòs, using an integrated approach including environmental, social, demographic and climate problems (City of Barcelona 2019a, City of Barcelona 2019b). The Barcelona 2017-2027 Strategy for Inclusion and Reducing Social Inequality in Barcelona states that *“Barcelona considers it a priority to reduce inequalities in income and safeguard the social rights of its residents, as a means to increasing fairness and training and educational opportunities, and to strengthening social and community support networks for eradicating stigmatization and segregation and reducing territorial inequalities.”* (p. 5) (City of Barcelona 2017b). The City Council has shown their commitment to reducing inequality by increasing budget dedications, increasing activities of social organizations and the strengthening of social movements geared towards this goal (p. 57) (City of Barcelona 2017b).

1. *How will climate change and water availability affect the livability of Barcelona?*

Even with major mitigation efforts, the IPCC has projected a tendency towards further global warming in the 21st century. As a result, the amount of snow and ice will diminish, and heat waves, (extreme) droughts, and floods will occur more frequently (Della-Marta, Haylock et al. 2007, Della-Marta, Luterbacher et al. 2007, Perkins and Alexander 2012, Perkins, Alexander et al. 2012, IPCC 2014, Zampieri, Russo et al. 2016). This will affect water availability and water quality and related waterborne and vector-borne infectious diseases (Delpha, Jung et al. 2009, Whitehead, Wilby et al. 2009, EEA 2017). More heat stress (Scoccimarro, Fogli et al. 2017)(Scoccimarro, Fogli et al. 2017) - especially in urban areas - may occur if no adaptation measures are implemented (Kleerekoper, Van Esch et al. 2012, EEA 2017). Especially in Southern Europe, freshwater is scarce in summers (EC 2013) and the demands of multiple users increase in these periods (e.g. agriculture, cooling water, bathing water, drinking water). This may lead to further water quality deterioration, higher water temperatures, and the intrusion of salt-water into aquifers and agricultural land due to depletion of natural resources as is already ongoing (EEA 2008, Foster and Custodio 2019).

Increased river flows during winter and lower river flows during summer have been recorded since the 1960s in large parts of Europe (EC 2013). It is also projected to result in strong changes of river flows and their extremes across Europe.

The City Council of Barcelona states that its city, as a place where people, economic activities, a dense infrastructure and facilities are highly concentrated, is vulnerable to the effects of climate change (City of Barcelona 2013, City of Barcelona 2018c). Droughts and torrential rain have been problems related to climate and water that the city has faced for decades. The challenge to cope with these issues will likely become more pronounced due to the effects of climate change. This observation is supported by the modelling shown in Figure 4.1. The figure shows the projected change of the number of summer days (> 25°C) for the Barcelona Metropolitan Area towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005, based on EURO-CORDEX modelling (see Annex II). It should be noted that the results for Barcelona have a tendency to underestimate compared to real data (currently approximately 80 summer days per year), but do show a significant increase towards 2100.

Another important challenge for the city, in terms of costs and technical issues, is the expansion of waste water infrastructures and storm water storage capacity, in order to be prepared for more intense and frequent rainfall and flooding, while at the same time preserving the water quality (City of Barcelona 2013).

Figure 4.1 Projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) in the Barcelona region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005.

3. *How will political and institutional developments have an impact on decision-making within the domains of water and health in the city?*

There are two major developments with strong implications for current and future water management:

- Reorganisation of governance and subsidiarity at the level of municipalities and autonomous communities, which influences how roles and responsibilities are assigned to (other) governmental bodies for different water management functions;
- Innovation of financing mechanisms (public/private) at different scales for “who is responsible for what and who will pay for what”.

Additional challenges in the nearby future include:

- Digital reformation and increasing interconnectedness that trigger new ways of organizing local public services;

- The decreasing trust of citizens in their governments may lead to changes in the role of citizens in water policy in order to secure social and political acceptability. This can take place by engagement of citizens and stakeholders in the realisation of urban water ambitions. This may also contribute to an increased awareness on water risks;
- An increasing awareness amongst citizens is needed regarding their role in environmental water quality and quantity through consumption and lifestyle (e.g. (Staatsen, Van der Vliet et al. 2017)).
- In 2018 a drought protocol was incorporated into Barcelona's basic emergency plan. The protocol describes the measures and actions that should be taken in case of drought in order to protect basic water services and tackle potential shortages (City of Barcelona 2018a).

4. *Will new water management technology be a solution for Barcelona's future water and climate challenges?*

The trend towards healthier urban living environments is further stimulated by digitalisation. Increased environmental surveillance through small-scale sensors and environmental quality forecasting enhances the ambition for clean urban environments. That is, exposure to contaminants is minimal, the opportunities for physical exercise and mental relaxation are high. Digitalisation may stimulate the development of smart urban water management, including smart climate resilient water management like efficient use of water storage capacity and the use of storm water overflows. This will affect the quality of the living environment (both built and natural), water availability, and the acceleration towards a climate resilient infrastructure (Sedlak 2015). With big data management, governments will have more opportunities to manage urban transportation, water and energy resources, and waste efficiently (OECD 2016). Large scale implementation of decentralised wastewater systems that are possibly more efficient, could affect performance and management of centralised sewer systems to a large extent, although progress towards adoption and implementation of these decentralised systems is slow. Key barriers reported in literature include investments, organisational challenges, and the absence of a prohibitive regulatory framework (e.g., (Spiller and Zeeman 2013, Guimarães, Malheiros et al. 2016)). Barcelona is expanding the sewerage network and invested 45.4 million euros in the improvement of its infrastructures in 2018 (<https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/premsa/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/clavegueram.pdf>).

This is needed as a response to effects of climate change and coincides with the need to be a resilient city. More intense rainfall and the rise in sea level will result in flood risk of the city. Therefore the hydraulic capacity of the drainage system is now being increased. Improvements also involve a new integrated management system of the urban sewerage network, which will include a system of solutions aimed at controlling and reducing the impact of untreated sewage spills during storms. This consequent water quality improvement could support the development of healthy blue spaces, a possible co-benefit of such an investment programme.

5. *How will the city of Barcelona cope with an ageing population in the coming decades?*

Life expectancy at birth for men is expected to increase by 7.2 years, from 77.6 in 2013 to 84.7 in 2060 (Eurostat 2017). Life expectancy at birth will increase by 6.0 years for women, from 83.1 in 2013 to 89.1 in 2060, implying a convergence of life expectancy between males and females. There is considerable disparity in life expectancy between EU countries in the absolute levels. Spain ranks first in the EU, with an average (males and females) life expectancy of 83.5 years. In addition to life expectancy, health and wellbeing are important to the quality of life. Older people are more vulnerable

for water-related infectious diseases and heat stress in absence of water. Other effects might be a changing occurrence of age-related diseases and a changing private/work/care balance for the working population. The shift in age groups might call for different needs regarding urban water use, both in terms of availability and water quality, like the use for bathing and other water activities or enjoying the views. By 2030 almost a third of Barcelona's residents will be 60 years old or more (City of Barcelona 2018b). Currently, 80 percent of people over 65 live in their own homes, without any pending payments. However, with rents in the city continuously rising, and reduced access to property, vulnerability of elderly in terms of access to affordable and suitable housing is likely to increase.

By 2030 almost a third of Barcelona's residents will be 60 years old or more. Currently, 80 percent of people over 65 live in their own homes. However, with rents in the city continuously rising, and reduced access to property, vulnerability of elderly in terms of access to affordable and suitable housing is likely to increase (Ajuntament de Barcelona 2018b).

The Barcelona City is well aware of the demographic changes that it is facing in the coming decades and aims to 'anticipate municipal policies which adapt to demographic change and adjust services and facilities to the needs of future generations' (Municipality of Barcelona, 2018b). One of the proposed interventions that should improve access to services for elderly citizens is to create 'care superblocks' where social services and community spaces for elderly are concentrated per neighborhood. Another planned intervention is the development of 'senior citizen friendly paths'. Analyses of social profiles at the neighborhood level and vulnerable groups within the municipality are part of the information needed to develop these plans (Municipality of Barcelona, 2018).

The 2017-2027 Strategy for Inclusion and Reducing Social Inequality in Barcelona explicitly expresses concerns about inequities of ageing populations and states that: "A friendly city that promotes healthy active ageing based on the personal and social independence of elderly people and their central role in shaping the city." (p. 64 https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/dretssocials/sites/default/files/arxiu-documents/strategy_inclusion_2017-2027_en.pdf). The plan also stresses the need for informal care for elderly, but that no one should rely on solely one person to be responsible for such care (p. 100).

4.2 BlueHealth ambitions for Barcelona in 2040

During the workshop, two values were identified as dominant for Barcelona: climate resilience and promoting social equity. These values have been used as the basis for normative views on Barcelona in 2040 regarding BlueHealth. The information from the Trend scenario was used to identify challenges and opportunities that arise from these trends and what should be done to realize these views. Input on interventions was abstracted from the discussion during the workshop. These two values, the underlying trends and possibilities to achieve a more desirable future have been assimilated into two storylines: 'Protecting water as a basic vital resource' and 'A healthy, socially fair and safe Barcelona'.

4.2.1 'Protecting water as a basic vital resource'

Desired future

The city of Barcelona is a self-sufficient city with zero emissions by 2050. This means that by 2040 the city needs to be well on its way to reach these goals. Moreover, Barcelona will proactively tackle challenges related to climate change, thereby adding value to the city and guaranteeing quality of life for its residents (City of Barcelona 2013). With the prospects of a rising sea level, rising temperatures and more extremes in rainfall and periods of drought, meeting the demand for water and providing clean and good quality water are important challenges. In 2040 there is a sufficient supply of clean drinking water, and the available water in the city is used efficiently. Barcelona's citizens, companies and visitors are well aware of the importance of efficient water use. Green and blue corridors in the city offer shade and cooling during warm periods and help to retain water.

Challenges and opportunities on the way to climate resilience

Challenges:

- The effects of climate change will become significant towards the end of the 21st century and thus beyond the timescale of this scenario (2040) (Rajczak and Schär 2017). Even so, extreme weather events (heavy rainfall, mainly in winter, heat waves and periods of drought) will occur more frequently in the coming decades in the Barcelona Metropolitan Area (City of Barcelona 2013, KNMI 2014, Rajczak and Schär 2017, City of Barcelona 2018c).
- Climate resilience calls for measures to adapt for water excess and water shortages, and related issues towards water quality. On the one hand, Barcelona will need more water resources in the coming decades; on the other hand more rainwater retention and drainage systems are needed. Due to the long lifetimes of urban infrastructure, effects beyond 2040 need to be accounted for in current long term urban planning as well (City of Barcelona 2018c).
- Long periods of high temperatures and drought may lead to algal blooms and the development of water quality problems due to the low base flow in the surface water and ongoing inputs from various activities.
- Investments in good quality of surface waters attribute to the attractiveness of the city to live in, but could also attribute to more gentrification and widen the social gap.
- Climate justice: Climate change will not affect all people and neighbourhoods in the same way ((City of Barcelona 2018c). This could lead to a strong increase in deaths due to increased incidence of heat waves and ageing population in some more deprived neighbourhoods (ISGlobal data).

Opportunities:

- Increasing the surface of blue and green spaces in the city to retain water and form a source of cooling and shade during warm periods in summer (nature-based solutions).
- Informing the general public and raising awareness on the importance of efficient water use, especially in periods of droughts. Further implementing the drought protocol from 2018.

Interventions contributing to resilience and health

Interventions in multiple policy domains, e.g. related to work, income, housing, transport, can affect climate resilience and health directly or indirectly. This especially holds in urban environments with a high density of activities and usages of space and complex social interactions. Within this future scenario for Barcelona we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to climate resilience and health. Instruments to adapt the outdoor environment to the effects of climate change in ways that are beneficial to health generally include interventions in blue and green spaces, like water squares or playgrounds. Other types of interventions focus on raising awareness among citizens and companies, effectiveness of governance arrangements and robust and healthy urban design.

Adapting the built environment to anticipate climate change

Both buildings and public spaces should be adapted to the changing climate in order to become more resilient. Greening public space can lead to several benefits for public health and climate resilience. More green space and attractive, accessible blue spaces can contribute to people's mental health and wellbeing, they can provide shade and cooling during warm periods in summer (reducing the urban heat island effect) and retain water in periods of heavy rainfall (nature based solutions) (Naturvation 2019). Introducing green roofs might be a good strategy to increase green spaces in cities with pressure on space. Green roofs could help mitigate the effects of climate change by improving building insulation, increasing biodiversity, and improving rainwater management. It also stimulates local food production and creates a recreation and meeting area for building inhabitants that can contribute to social interaction among neighbours (City of Barcelona 2013). Climate proof-building is another way to creating a more climate resilient city. For example, by installing carbon-efficient warming and cooling techniques instead of using air-conditioning or electric heating.

A heat protocol

A heat protocol was set up recently to raise awareness among citizens on how to act during heatwaves (http://interior.gencat.cat/en/arees_dactuacio/proteccio_civil/consells_autoproteccio_emergencia/riscos_naturals/onada_de_calor/index.html). The protocol (POCS – *Plan de actuación para prevenir los efectos de las olas de calor sobre la salud*) is embedded within the Spanish framework (Plan Nacional de Actuaciones Preventivas por Altas Temperaturas (https://www.mscbs.gob.es/ciudadanos/saludAmbLaboral/planAltasTemp/2019/Plan_nacional_actuaciones_preventivas.htm)), but has defined additional preventive actions.

The objectives of the POCS are:

- Predict potentially dangerous weather situations.
- Minimize the negative effects of heat waves on the health of the population in Catalonia.
- Coordinate the measures and resources existing in Catalonia to face a possible heat wave.

The plan is updated every year around May by the Public Health Agency (www.salutpublica.gencat.cat/). Active engagement with neighbourhood groups could support a further implementation and realise a better response towards elderly and vulnerable groups (e.g. young children and chronically ill).

Monitoring and communication

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and develop an adaptation strategy in case measures do not lead to the expected result. Barcelona's Climate Plan (City of Barcelona 2018c) includes indicators that will be used to monitor its outcomes every 2 years.

Improving and promoting public transport

New developments like the Barcelona Superllas (Superblock) plan are supposed to lead to more green space and fewer cars to improve climate resilience and less air pollution (Mueller, Rojas-Rueda et al. 2019, City of Barcelona 2019c).

Improving the treatment and reuse of waste water

Water saving and water reuse initiatives could counter water scarcity. Initiatives that entail a reduced emission of effluent to the surface water also contribute to chemical and ecological water quality improvement and the use of these waters for health (Jensen, Lauridsen et al. 2015).

4.2.2 'A healthy, socially fair and safe Barcelona'

Desired future

In 2040 Barcelona is a healthy city, where active living is promoted, where you can breathe clean air and enjoy quality public spaces, and people's health and well-being is guaranteed. The diversity of Barcelona's citizens is taken into account when applying policies and measures, creating socially fair governance of the city. People are able to live in comfort and social cohesion, with quality green areas. Barcelona generates safe, friendly spaces that are suitable for everyone (City of Barcelona 2018c).

Challenges and opportunities on the way to a healthy, socially fair and safe Barcelona

Challenges:

- Wealth and health are unequally distributed between neighbourhoods. More vulnerable people and poorer neighborhoods will likely be more affected by the climate change. This might lead to an increase in the vulnerable population threatened by energy poverty, health problems and the rising cost of living due to climate change. In addition, more income inequality will likely create more health inequalities too.
- Accessibility of housing for residents in lower income groups and, especially for elderly housing that is suited to their needs.
- Equal access to blue and green spaces in and close to the city.
- Different groups use (blue) public space in different, sometimes conflicting ways.

Opportunities:

- Create more public spaces that invite residents and visitors to active mobility (walking, biking), especially in more deprived neighbourhoods (e.g. SuperIllas (City of Barcelona 2019c)).
- Include perceptions, needs and ideas of different stakeholders, especially neighbourhood residents in plans for creating more blue and green spaces within the city.

Interventions contributing to equity and inclusiveness

Improve awareness and interaction

Evidence based, transparent and understandable data helps to raise awareness among the general public on the value of blue spaces for health. It is important that these communication and engagement practices address different age groups, gender and cultural diverse groups in multi languages and anticipate on the different users of blue spaces (children facilities, sports, bicycling, elderly, open plains, no lanes, accessibility for all).

Monitoring and communication

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and, in case measures do not lead to expected results, also develop an adaptation strategy.

Involvement of local community

Involvement of the local community to get a better understanding of local needs, to use local knowledge on what works and what doesn't (local community process with combination of people that have a lot of knowledge and less knowledge) and to promote participation for decision making. Barcelona has a tradition of involving citizens and involvement through stakeholder meetings are common. This is for example organized through the digital platform "Decidim" (<https://decidim.org/>), that aims to facilitate community participation in cities and organizations. Examples of current citizen involvement projects are about the *Strategic plan of the coastal areas of the city* and the Low Emission Zone that is expected to be implemented in January 2020 (<https://www.decidim.barcelona/processes>).

Creating accessible public green and blue spaces for all so different activities can take place

In 2016, an urban riverside regeneration project for the Besòs river was implemented to facilitate access to the riverbank for pedestrians and cyclists. A study done by ISGlobal showed that there was a 25% increase in users of the renovated area of the river after the intervention. There was an increase in sedentary users and those engaged in moderate levels of physical activity. The growth of users was mainly driven by females, adults, children, and the non-Caucasian population. In general, resident interviewees were happy to live near the river, and were satisfied with the intervention. Moreover, interviewees thought living near the riverside area might benefit their health and wellbeing (Vert, Carrasco-Turigas et al. 2019b). The health and health-related economic impacts associated with physical activity in this urban riverside

park regeneration project were estimated to result in an annual reduction of 7.3 deaths (95% CI: 5.4; 10.2), and 6.2 cases of diseases (95% CI: 2.0; 11.6). These health benefits correspond to 11.9 DALYs (95% CI: 3.4; 20.5) and an annual health-economic impact of 23.4 million euros (95% CI: 17.2 million; 32.8 million) (Vert, Fleming et al. 2019a). This underlines that improving the accessibility of public green and blue spaces can result in health and health-related economic benefits.

4.3 Wrap up BlueHealth Futures for Barcelona

There are income inequalities in Barcelona and there is a strong spatial concentration of poverty in a number of neighbourhoods. Low income groups are at risk of poor health outcomes, have less resources to adapt to effects of climate change, and are at risk of social exclusion. Climate change, and associated extreme weather, and fresh water availability will put pressure on the liveability of Barcelona and related adverse health effects will occur if no adaptation measures are implemented.

By 2030 almost a third of Barcelona's residents will be 60 years old or older. Access to affordable housing is likely to decrease with rents in the city continuously rising, and reduced availability of suitable housing for example due to tourism. The ageing population will be especially vulnerable to housing shortage, and non-optimal housing might further contribute to morbidity and mortality due to heat waves in this population.

Major political and institutional developments with strong implications on water management in Barcelona are expected to happen. The reorganization of governance and subsidiarity at the level of municipalities and regions and the innovation of financing mechanisms (public/private) at different scales make roles and responsibilities for different water management functions less clear and potentially less effective. However, new water management technologies and increasing awareness amongst citizens regarding their role in surface water quality and drinking water consumption may aid Barcelona's future water and climate challenges.

5 BlueHealth Futures: Trends and ambitions for Plymouth

5.1 BlueHealth trends for Plymouth

Plymouth, coined “Britain’s Ocean City” in 2013, has a remarkable rich heritage beginning as a fishing village with a population of about 3,500 in the 16th century. The city is situated at the south-west coast of England, in the county of Devon. Plymouth is famous for its associations with Sir Francis Drake and the defeat of the Spanish Armada in 1588, the departure point for the Pilgrim Fathers on board the Mayflower to North America in 1620 and a major base for the Royal Navy, the largest in western Europe, which still generates around 10% of the city’s income and employs around 2,500 service personnel and civilians. However, it was also heavily bombed in the Second World War and has a number of areas categories as highly deprived.

As of 2016, it had 264,000 inhabitants and under the unitary authority of the Plymouth City Council it covers a total surface area of 30.82 sq mi (79.83 km²) with a population density of about 8,500/sq mi (3,300/km²). As a maritime community with an international recognition in trade, emigration, exploration, and ocean science, it is located right on the sea coast in the south-west of England with 33% of its coastal infrastructure classed as ‘artificial’ (i.e. sea walls and rock armour revetment) (Knights, Firth et al. 2016)

BlueHealth trends for Plymouth in 2040

What developments will Plymouth be facing in the coming decades when it comes to its urban waters and its potential to affect public health and well-being? What are relevant trends if we project current developments to the future?

During an interactive, multidisciplinary stakeholder workshop on December 12th, 2018 in Plymouth, experts from the local council, water and housing sectors, and community engagement specialists all attended, hoping to identify values and ambitions for the city. During the discussions, five trends related to these questions, have been identified as dominant for Plymouth. For this assessment, a longlist of trends was analysed, which was assembled using the DESTEP (demography, economy, social-cultural, technology, ecology and climate, political-institutional) methodology (RIVM 2014). In this trend scenario, we focus upon those five trends, that cover three of the DESTEP categories.

Which demographic trends are relevant for Plymouth?

- Increasing life expectancy

How do social-cultural or economic trends affect Plymouth?

- More waterfront development for urban regeneration
- Changes in income distribution
- More recreational use of blue spaces

What trends regarding ecology and the environment are important in Plymouth?

- Loss of biodiversity due to humans

Description of trends for Plymouth

1. How will increasing life expectancy influence life in Plymouth?

In EU-28 Member States, life expectancy at birth for males is expected to increase by 7.2 years, from 77.6 in 2013 to 84.7 in 2060 (Eurostat 2017). Life expectancy at birth is projected to increase by 6.0 years for females, from 83.1 in 2013 to 89.1 in 2060, implying a convergence of life expectancy between males and females. There is considerable variation between EU countries in the absolute levels, but all countries show similar trends. In addition to life expectancy, health and wellbeing are important to the quality of life. Older people are more vulnerable for water-related infectious diseases and heat stress in absence of water. Other effects might be a changing frequency of age-related diseases and a changing private/work/care balance for the working population. The shift in age groups might call for different options regarding urban water use, both in terms of availability and water quality.

In Plymouth, the age groups 60-65 years and over 90 have shown the biggest increase over the last 10 years. The biggest percentage decrease was shown for the 40-44 and 35-39 year olds in this period. Plymouth's population continues to grow, with a projected increase of 7% by 2034. There will be a shift in the population structure of Plymouth over the next 20 years as the proportion of the population aged 65 and over increases (see Figure 5.1). The Office for National Statistics (ONS) projects a rise in the percentage of the population in this age group, from 17.8 per cent in 2016 to 22.3 per cent by 2034. However, it is predicted that Plymouth's population will age more slowly than in the South West or in England. This is reflected by a 33.7 per cent increase in the number of people aged 65 or over between 2016 and 2034 (an additional 15,900 individuals) compared to a 42.9 per cent increase in the South West and a 44.0 per cent increase in England. Life expectancy varies strongly across the city; from 86.5 years in the Plympton Chaddlewood ward to 76.4 years in Drake (Plymouth City Council 2017).

Figure 5.1 Plymouth's current and projected 2034 populations (Plymouth City Council 2017).

2. What will be the influence of urban development and economy on water and health?

Waterfronts in European cities are increasingly redeveloped into attractive and healthy blue spaces for citizens, tourist and employees, emphasizing the connection of the city with the water and natural space. The city of Plymouth has a long history of waterfront regeneration from former functions as a naval port and dockyard, to residential, leisure, tourism, and heritage uses (Essex and Ford 2015). More tourism could include more public spending leading to higher incomes for people in the service industry and an increased sense of pride to be a 'Plymouthian or janner'. Depending on the course of urban developments and decisions made by governments, waterfront regeneration can be more or less inclusive to all citizens.

The proportion of residents in Plymouth experiencing deprivation due to low income has increased in recent years (11.5 per cent of the Plymouth population in 2015). This proportion varies throughout the city, but the areas experiencing the relatively highest deprivation are situated relatively close to the waterfront (Plymouth City Council 2017).. The city remains a relatively low wage economy with over 20 per cent of the city's households earning less than £17,500 and over half earning less than £27,000. Alongside this, the proportion of those excluded from the labour market in Plymouth has been increasing since 2010. Over 29 per cent of adults in Plymouth are already over indebted, one of the highest levels in the country and the highest in the South West. 7,308 children under the age of 16 (15.9 per cent of the total in this age-group) are living in income deprived households, with a strong variation between individual neighbourhoods and are thus likely to be experiencing child poverty (Plymouth City Council 2017).

Income inequality is expected to rise further in the UK (Hood and Waters 2017, Corlett, Bangham et al. 2018). Higher inequity in society is correlated with greater social unrest. Access to blue space may be better for high income groups (e.g. higher property values when

properties face water (Luttik 2000). In general, income inequality may have a negative effect on environmental quality (e.g. (Camilo Cardenas, Stranlund et al. 2002, Drabo 2011)). Differences between different neighborhoods will become more pronounced. Centrally located districts often are upgraded by an influx of more affluent residents (retired people and city dwellers buying second homes in Plymouth) resulting in higher quality of living to higher incomes for people in the service industry but also increasing home prices. This process is referred to as gentrification. Simultaneously, lower income households are forced to move to neighborhoods with lower housing costs. These neighborhoods are often characterized by a clustering of other unfavorable factors as well, such as higher crime rates and low environmental quality. In Plymouth, gentrification can be identified. Income inequalities can also cause health and wellbeing problems. Quality improvements of waterfront and access to waterfront may lead to health gains. Characteristics (of waterfronts) in Plymouth are key for its attractiveness to tourists, citizens and economic activities.

The recreational use of blue spaces will increase in the future, under influence of tourism and popularity of water-related activities in urban areas.

Worldwide, the popularity of recreational activities has grown. This includes water related activities, for example in both inland and marine waters. Moreover, the ease of travel has altered the public use of water for recreational purposes (WHO 2005). Developments in technologies such as wetsuit design and water sports equipment (e.g. stand-up paddle boards) have added upon that. Nearly 70% of European tourists spend their holidays at a waterside location, mostly within other European countries, with around two billion days spent annually at coastal recreational resorts (EU 2015, ETA 2016).

Water can be used for a variety of recreational purposes, such as water sports, swimming, fishing, surfing, sailing, etc. Furthermore, the watersides can be attractive environments for relaxation, social activities and physical exercise. In some European countries, there is an emerging trend of recreation in water that is not designated for recreational purposes per se, such as swimming. This may increase risks of drowning and infectious diseases (WHO 2005, WHO 2017). In a broader sense, a trend can be identified that people visit nature not solely as a place to enjoy nature conservation, but also as a space with other usages, e.g. for water sports. As a consequence, more and more nature conservation areas are being used for recreational activities as well. Furthermore, water retention areas (temporary storage of surplus rainwater) in urban areas are sometimes also designed as water playgrounds and parks.

The 60 kilometres of Plymouth's waterfront (accounting for inlets), consisting of the land and the adjacent waters, is arguably the city's most valuable asset and is central to its identity as Britain's Ocean City and vision to become 'one of Europe's most vibrant waterfront cities' (Essex and Ford 2015).

In terms of waterfront development, Plymouth, like many other European cities, is experiencing transformation. In recent years, Devonport, Royal William Yard, Stonehouse, Millbay, the Barbican, and Sutton Harbour have undergone significant regeneration. Such reinvestment has formed the basis for a "[Waterfront Strategic Masterplan](#)" but there are some concerns that parts of potential redevelopment could gentrify some areas of the city (Essex and Ford, 2015). For example, the Royal William Yard, once used as a victualling depot of the Royal Navy was converted in more recent years into blocks of residential flats or apartments together with space for businesses, restaurants, and other cultural and artistic endeavours. Moreover, tackling the physical health and inactivity of residents is embedded in the vision of the Plymouth city authorities. This is currently being carried out through various outdoor- and nature-based programmes (e.g. (Richardson, Goss et al. 2013)).

3. *What are relevant trends related to ecology and the environment in Plymouth?*

The ecological impacts due to human activities (loss of biodiversity, pollution, habitat loss, fragmentation of natural areas, reduction in their size and depletion of natural resources) will increase. Globally, water bodies are subject to eutrophication, acidification, alien species, and the effects of climate change (UNEP 2007, EEA 2012). That might result in a loss of biodiversity, which has severe consequences for water-related ecosystem services (MEA 2005). Based on the European Water Framework Directive (WFD; 2000/60/EC) and the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; 2008/56/EC), the EU Member States are required to develop ecologically-based assessment systems for biological communities and to set river basin management plans to improve the ecological status of all water bodies. However, despite improvements in some regions, the deterioration of water ecosystems still occurs throughout Europe (EEA 2012). Decreasing water body ecological status is a threat to public health and incurs significant economic costs in the EU (Pretty, Mason et al. 2003, Dodds, Bouska et al. 2009). More than half of the European surface water bodies are in sub-optimal condition (EEA 2017).

Due to environmental changes blue spaces could become less attractive to visit (EEA 2012) and possible favourable conditions for waterborne infectious diseases could be introduced (Pretty, Mason et al. 2003, Brown, Medlock et al. 2014)(Pretty, Mason et al. 2003, Dodds, Bouska et al. 2009, Brown, Medlock et al. 2014). Well-executed waterfront renovations however, could also have a positive effect on biodiversity.

Over the years, Plymouth as a waterfront city has been working towards managing water to meet the increasing need of the population regarding affordable, quality, water and sanitation. Since 2013, the UK government has implemented a £50 reduction in household water bills to order to incentivise customers to sustainably reduce their surface drainage and lessen the burden of low income earners in the south-west of England more generally.

Furthermore, Plymouth is in the midst of creating the UK's first National Marine Park in the waters of Plymouth Sound. As well as a number of other goals such as highlighting its ecological quality and raising awareness of marine issues, its creation will also support the increased use of the water for sustainable recreational activities.

A survey of visitors undertaken in recent years by the Marine Biological Association revealed that terrestrial (on-land) recreational activities by the water were most popular among visitors to such coastal blue spaces. There were clear preferred locations that emerged from on-site surveys: the upper Tamar (Calstock-Cotehele area), the Tavy (Lopwell Dam – Bere Ferrers area), Hoe (Devil's Point to Barbican) and the coast path between Mount Batten and Wembury were all popular locations for recreational use of blue spaces.

An online survey indicated that the outer estuary and the open coast areas were most used, with much lower patterns of use in the upper Tamar and Tavy rivers. This pattern likely reflects the main access points to the European Marine Site and proximity to the main population centre of Plymouth. The most popular marine-based recreational activities were canoeing/kayaking, angling, sailing and swimming (Langmead, Tillin et al. 2017).

Climate change has not been identified as a dominant trend for Plymouth, except for the increase of storms. This observation is supported by Figure 5.2. The figure shows the projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) for the Plymouth region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005, based on EURO-CORDEX modelling (see Annex II). It should be noted that the results for Plymouth have a tendency to underestimate (currently approximately 3 summer days per year).

Figure 5.2 Projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) in the Plymouth region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005.

5.2 BlueHealth ambitions for Plymouth in 2040

During the workshop with experts and local professionals (December, 12th, 2018), two values related to water and health were identified as dominant for Plymouth: *access to blue spaces* and *valuing Plymouth's natural and cultural heritage*. These values have been used as the basis for normative views on Plymouth in 2040. The information from the trends scenario was used to identify challenges and opportunities that might be met when realizing these views. Input on interventions was abstracted from the discussion during the workshop.

5.2.1 'Access to Plymouth's blue spaces for all'

Desired future

Blue spaces in the city of Plymouth are accessible for all inhabitants and visitors and are pleasant places to be and use in 2040. The municipality has anticipated adequately on different needs of the people within in its community and shaped attractive blue spaces that are available to people from different backgrounds and age groups. These ambitions coincide with the goals laid down in the local policy plan to 'support strong and inclusive communities where people have a sense of belonging and ownership, feel safe and confident, with the opportunity to live, work and play in good quality sustainable *neighbourhoods*' towards 2034. The need for safer and more attractive and accessible blue spaces is used to engage citizens in participatory processes for future spatial developments. Easier access to blue spaces benefits the creation of a healthy living environment, promoting the attractiveness of Plymouth's waterfront and creating more opportunities for social events and healthy activities for it's citizens.

Challenges and opportunities on the way to accessible blue spaces for all

Challenges:

- Social inequalities and differences in needs and preferences might negatively influence the accessibility of blue spaces for all. When including the community in plans for the development of blue spaces, it is therefore important to have an inclusive and open process of participation, with an active role of the community.
- Regeneration of the public space and the construction of new homes might negatively impact the affordability of the area alongside the water, creating an economic barrier to live next to the water for those residents that are less affluent (and thereby inducing a process of gentrification).
- Development in blue spaces just beyond the Hoe or the Barbican. These areas are now the primary focus in city planning.

Opportunities:

- Mayflower 2020 memorial and more arrivals of cruiseships creates momentum for investments in public space that can have a positive impact on the community's health in the future. Other effects may be higher incomes and job security.
- Investing in attractive and accessible blue spaces might create more opportunities for tourism by cultural, educational and leisure activities along the waterfronts.
- Accessible and attractive public blue spaces can encourage physical and social engagement (f.e. volunteering) of elderly. Moreover, the exposure to pleasant blue spaces can have a positive impact on the health of (elderly) inhabitants of Plymouth.

Interventions contributing to accessibility of blue spaces and health

Interventions in multiple policy domains can affect accessible public spaces, public engagement and health directly or indirectly. These interventions can be related to governance, spatial planning, community involvement and environment. Within this future scenario for Plymouth, we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to the realization of access for all related to the topic of water and health. Interventions that contribute to inclusiveness have a focus on engaging the local community in planning and ensuring spatial developments that serve different groups in society.

Involving the local community in spatial planning

The city of Plymouth and districts of South West Devon are together working on a local plan for future developments. One aspect of the plan covers managing and enhancing Plymouth's waterfront. The aim of the planned waterfront renewal is to create a 'unique, characteristic, sustainable and vibrant asset that drives the city's economic, cultural, social and environmental wellbeing' (<https://plymswdevonplan.co.uk/policy/so3/ply20>). The plan covers the inclusion of local authorities during the planning process and aims at delivering a healthy city with qualitative public spaces. To ensure the plans coincide with the wishes and needs of different groups (age, income, 'janners' and new-comers) within the local community they should be consulted and involved in the plans for renewal of the waterfront and neighbouring public spaces. This especially counts for the people who live and already make use of the affected space.

Create public spaces that invite to engage in healthy activities

Creating public spaces where accessibility by foot and bike are the central point of focus, thereby stimulating active mobility (e.g. <http://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/environment-and-health/urban-health/activities/healthy-urban-design> (WHO), <https://www.healthyrbandevelopment.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/Healthy-Urban-Planning-Checklist-March-2014.pdf> (UK), <https://www.health.nsw.gov.au/urbanhealth/Publications/healthy-urban-dev-check.pdf> (Australia)).

For example for employees who want to walk or bike to their work or citizens who want to go for a run or a walk along the waterfront, but also create the ability for elderly to go from the old town to the waterfront. Moreover, it is important to make the public space accessible for people with disabilities or limited mobility, for example by creating points of encounter where people can meet and take a rest (RIVM, 2019).

Health checks in urban design

Use or create blue spaces to increase storage capacity during heavy rainfall, but include health aspects in design and operation to avoid microbiological contamination. The adaptive multi-layer safety approach as has been developed in Amsterdam in 2013 to anticipate on the increased risk of flooding (prevention, sustainable spatial design, crisis management) can be combined with the ambitions on a healthy outdoor environment, to decrease potential risks and get health benefits from new projects. For this purpose, the adaptive approach has to be complemented with health based criteria (e.g. (Schets, De Man et al. 2017). City planners and project developers use these criteria to test applications for new spatial initiatives (e.g. <https://www.urbangreenbluegrids.com/design-tool/>).

Improving water quality, reduction of the number of overflows

Storm water overflows and leakage from aged sewages systems may impact the safety of bathing water by microbiological contamination. Recent investment programmes have been undertaken to ensure bathing water quality by improving key stormwater overflows across the city, removing surface water from the sewerage network in Cattedown and increasing stormwater storage capacity in Stonehouse (<https://www.southwestwater.co.uk/about-us/latest-news/news-2018/26million-plymouth-wastewater-upgrades-complete/>).

Monitoring and communication

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important

to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and develop an adaptation strategy in case measures do not lead to the expected result.

5.2.2 'Valuing Plymouth's natural and cultural heritage'

Desired future

In 2040 Plymouth's unique cultural heritage is an asset that *interests and serves* local inhabitants or janners, *creates economic value* and attracts tourism. The regeneration of the city's waterfront creates new opportunities for *business*, recreation, health and biodiversity. At the same time Plymouth's natural networks are maintained and enhanced, providing the green and blue natural spaces needed to support the social and economic wellbeing of Plymouth as well as safeguarding the natural environment for future generations.

Challenges and opportunities towards valuing Plymouth's natural and cultural heritage

Challenges:

- The naval dock yard in Plymouth has been an important source of employment for centuries. In the past decades the number of jobs has strongly diminished. In order to keep the local economy viable and sustainable, more diversification is necessary.
- Social and economic differences between 'old' and 'new' inhabitants Plymouth
- Maintaining and enhancing a viable and sustainable economy that benefits the whole society, and not increases inequalities.
- Old sewage water infrastructure and overflows may impose risks to water quality
- More data / knowledge needed on usage of heritage features (natural or manmade) by different groups.
- Effects of climate change
- Negative impact of tourism

Opportunities:

- While the importance the marine and naval industry is declining in Plymouth due to its planned move, it's cultural heritage could function as an asset to diversify the local economy.
- Mayflower 2020 as an incentive to initiate developments regarding waterfront development, reduction of social inequalities and cultural heritage.
- Overflow developments
- The regeneration of Plymouth's waterfront has become a central point in the future plans of the city council (Essex, 2015; <https://plymswdevonplan.co.uk/policy/so3>). More access to the sea, and a stronger connection with the water opens up the possibility for activities and new uses that directly and indirectly can be beneficial to the wellbeing and health of the citizens of Plymouth.

Interventions contributing to enhancing natural and cultural heritage and health

Interventions in multiple policy domains, e.g. related to culture, housing, economy, spatial planning and the natural environment can affect the attractiveness and value of Plymouth's natural and cultural heritage directly or indirectly. Within this future scenario for Plymouth we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to the realization of valuing its natural and cultural heritage to the topic of water and health. Interventions that aim at maintaining and creating natural and cultural value have a focus on communication and engagement.

Plymouth Sound Marine Park

Designating a Marine park in Plymouth Sound could boost public engagement, create awareness, protect the local environment and culture and create economic opportunities (Plymouth City Council 2019).

Creating awareness on natural, cultural and historic value of place

Events like the Mayflower 2020 anniversary, but also information signs and maintaining the value of heritage in future developments create opportunities to engage inhabitants and visitors and inform them on the unique identity of Plymouth's blue spaces. This can contribute to a local sense of place and pride, and might generate more (business) opportunities for tourism and recreation.

Involvement of local community

Involvement of local community to get a better understanding of local needs and differences within the community, to use local knowledge on what works and what doesn't (local community process with combination of people that have a lot of knowledge and less knowledge) and to promote participation for decision making.

5.3 Wrap-up BlueHealth Futures for Plymouth

In Plymouth, demographic changes, especially increases in life expectancy and an ageing population, are expected to affect equitable access to more natural waterfront areas and also how health co-benefits that might arise from waterfront areas for this population could be exploited.

Waterfront redevelopment, an impactful global trend in Plymouth, could bring economic benefits and may lead to increases in people employed in the service industry, thereby aiding the local economy. However, such redevelopment might also pose risks to gentrification of the city, potentially 'pricing out' its poorer residents of home ownership. This also relates to another important economic trend, namely growing income inequality in the city. These trends might threaten Plymouth's identity, a value identified as particularly important to Plymouth.

A positive future trend is the increase in recreational activities at blue spaces as a way of both improving the health of the population through physical activity, as well as a means of underlining one of the city's key assets—its waterfront—in being unique among UK cities in inviting such a range of recreational water-based activities.

As an ecological trend, further loss of biodiversity might occur due to human impacts (which could be related to the trend of increasing recreation at waterfronts), but stakeholders also noted that the designation of Plymouth Sound as the UK's first National Marine Park may go some way to protecting marine ecosystems.

Equitable access to blue spaces is one of Plymouth's main ambitions and is in line with other policy plans to 'support inclusive communities' where individuals have agency over 'good quality sustainable neighbourhoods'. To meet the health needs of the population purported to benefit from it, participation of the public in creating safer, more attractive, and more accessible blue spaces is vital. Strategies discussed which might realise these ambitions included: (a) the involvement of the public in spatial planning, (b) using health evidence as the basis for the physical redesign of blue spaces, (c) utilising tools that consider health risks and benefits for

different population groups during the planning of a redesign, (d) improving the ecological quality of spaces, and (e) the early engagement of stakeholders in the planning process.

The second key ambition is a proper valuing of Plymouth's natural and cultural heritage. The city's maritime heritage is a key asset which both serves local inhabitants, but also attracts economic investment in waterfronts and tourism. There is a tension between future redevelopment of the waterfront as benefiting the economy but potentially threatening the city's identity, and stakeholders recognised the need to safeguard coastal ecosystems and waterfront areas more generally in order to preserve a distinct identity. Opportunities in realising this ambition included: (a) capitalising on the decline of the naval industry by creating jobs which use naval skills and thus creating a new job sector which thrives on the city's maritime heritage, (b) using the Mayflower 2020 celebrations as a platform for strengthening the city's cultural identity, (c) the possibility of keeping redevelopments true to the cultural heritage of the city, and (d) seeing redevelopment as an opportunity to increase people's contact with coastal and marine environments in the hope that in doing so, people will realise the cultural value of the coast to the city.

6 BlueHealth Futures: Trends and ambitions for Tallinn

6.1 BlueHealth trends for Tallinn

In the Middle Ages, Tallinn (or Reval, formerly used German reference) was part of national and international trade as a Hanseatic city. In the sixteenth century, the power of Germany and the Reformation ended the power of the Hanseatic League. Tallinn lost its influential position in the Baltic region. Tallinn joined the Swedish Kingdom in an attempt to resist attacks from Russia, but since the 18th century Tallinn belonged to the Russian Empire. Tallinn as a capital of Estonia gained independence from 1918. In 1940, the Soviet Union resigned the previously signed treaty by reoccupying Estonia. The communist regime has made Tallinn a major satellite city of the Soviet Union for decades. Complete new districts were added to Tallinn where Soviet migrants were housed. Tallinn grew to half a million inhabitants in 1989. After the breakup of the Soviet Union, in 1991, part of the former incomers (mostly military) left Tallinn. Nowadays about one third of the inhabitants of Tallinn are still Russian-speaking.

Tallinn is located in the northern part of the country, on the shore of the Gulf of Finland of the Baltic Sea, it has a population of 434,500 inhabitants in 2019 (32% of Estonia's population). Tallinn is a major financial, industrial, cultural, educational and research centre of Estonia. Tallinn is located south of Helsinki, Finland, west of Saint Petersburg, Russia, and east of Stockholm, Sweden. It has close historical ties with these three cities.

Tallinn has the highest number of start-ups per person among European countries and is a birthplace of many international high technology companies and platforms, including Skype, Transfer wise and BOLT. The city is to house the headquarters of the European Union's IT agency. Providing to the global cybersecurity it is the home to the NATO Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence. Tallinn is ranked as a global city and has been listed among the top ten digital cities in the world.

BlueHealth trends for Tallinn in 2040

What developments will Tallinn be facing in the coming decades when it comes to its urban waters and its potential to affect public health and well-being? What are relevant trends if we project current developments to the future?

During an interactive, multidisciplinary stakeholder workshop on April 16th, 2019 in Tallinn, expertise ranging from the environmental protection and nature conservation, water management, planning and municipality development, public health, social affairs, cultural endowment and community engagement all attended, hoping to identify values and ambitions for the city. As a result of the discussions, seven trends related to these questions, have been identified as most dominant for Tallinn. For this assessment, a longlist of trends was used as an input (Wuijts, De Vries et al. 2019), which was assembled using the DESTEP (demography, economy, social-cultural, technology, ecology and climate, political-institutional) methodology (RIVM 2014). In this trend scenario, we focus upon these seven trends, that have been clustered into four central themes:

1. *How will climate change and loss of biodiversity influence life in Tallinn?*
2. *How will demographic changes (e.g. ageing population) influence life in Tallinn?*
3. *How will increasing income inequality and waterfront regeneration affect Tallinn?*
4. *How will a (further) digitalisation of society influence life in Tallinn?*

Description of trends for Tallinn

1. How will climate change and loss of biodiversity influence life in Tallinn?

The ecological impacts (loss of biodiversity, pollution, depletion of natural resources) will increase due to human activities, such as economic development, and climate change. Water-related ecosystem services are subject to anthropogenic climate change as well as natural processes influencing the eutrophication and acidification of water bodies. These climate change effects can have negative consequences for water-related ecosystems services (MEA 2005). As part of the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; 2008/56/EC) and the European Water Framework Directive (WFD; 2000/60/EC), the EU Member States need to develop an ecological assessment for biological communities and to establish plans for the management of river basins in order to mitigate and improve the ecological status of all water bodies. However, despite improvements in some regions, the deterioration of water ecosystems still occurs throughout Europe (EEA 2012). Decreasing water body ecological status is a threat to public health and incurs significant economic costs in the EU (Pretty, Mason et al. 2003, Dodds, Bouska et al. 2009). More than half of the European surface water bodies are in sub-optimal condition (EEA 2017). Due to environmental changes blue spaces could become less attractive to visit (EEA 2012) and possible favourable conditions for waterborne infectious diseases could be introduced (Pretty, Mason et al. 2003, Dodds, Bouska et al. 2009, Brown, Medlock et al. 2014). Well-executed waterfront renovations however, could also have a positive effect on biodiversity.

Recent reports from the IPCC project a tendency towards a further increase of global warming in the 21st century despite current mitigation efforts (IPCC 2014). Therefore, the projected effects of global warming go well beyond the timescale of this trends scenario (2040) and extreme weather events (heat waves, droughts, more floods and sea-level rise) will occur more frequently in the coming decades in Europe (Perkins, Alexander et al. 2012, Cann, Thomas et al. 2013, IPCC 2014, KNMI 2014, Forzieri, Cescatti et al. 2017, Rajczak and Schär 2017). These events will have an impact on water availability as well as quality and related water- and vectorborne infectious diseases resulting in an increase of risk for the public health (Delpha, Jung et al. 2009, Whitehead, Wilby et al. 2009, EEA 2017). In addition to the aforementioned

risks, the increase of heat stress in urban areas could exacerbated the public health if no or limited adaptation measures are implemented (Kleerekoper et al., 2012; EEA, 2017; Wuijts et al., 2014, Scoccimarro et al., 2017).

During the stakeholder workshop in Tallinn, the further loss of biodiversity was identified as a highly relevant trend for the city of Tallinn, but official reports do not seem to support this observation.

In 2010, a strategic assessment has been made of the biodiversity in Tallinn city (Uustal, Kuldna et al. 2010). The assessment reveals that urban greenery, variety of ecosystems and species richness are in good status, but that biodiversity-oriented programmes, actions, projects and dedicated municipal budgets are scarcely represented in city plans. There are no studies published on the effects of more recent urbanization on the loss of biodiversity, although the municipality (City of Tallinn 2020) states that Tallinn is rich in biodiversity, basing on variability in landscapes and biotopes as well as preserved large urban green areas. Furthermore, an EU-wide comparison of urban green spaces by (EEA 2009) scores Tallinn among the greenest cities in the Europe. Figure 6.1 illustrates the gap between the perceived and reported green space in Tallinn.

Figure 6.1 Reported and perceived green space in European cities (EEA 2009).

Over the years, Tallinn has been working to improve its ecology and environment with the Tallinn Environmental Strategy 2030. Within this strategy, landscaping plays an important role, as it has been recognized that there is insufficient coherence and functioning links between the green network and residential areas. In addition, the government recognizes the essential role of bodies of water (including the sea) as an element of internal structure for the city. Therefore, the Estonian National Spatial Plan 2030+ aims to increase the linkage and

utilization of banks and bodies of water, by creating public points of access to areas that are in open and public use (National Spatial Plan Estonia 2030+, 2012). In regard to adaptation to climate change, the city has developed local adaptation measures. In 2009, Tallinn joined the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (<https://www.covenantofmayors.eu/en/>), and the Tallinn Sustainable Energy Action Plan 2011–2021 (SEAP, <https://oigusaktid.tallinn.ee/?id=3001&aktid=119834>) was established for performance of the obligations associated with the Covenant. The objective of the SEAP is to reduce CO₂ emissions in Tallinn by 20% by 2021. The objective established in the Tallinn Environmental Strategy 2030 (http://www.tallinn.ee/strateegia_inql) is to reduce CO₂ emissions by 40% in comparison to 2007.

The Tallinn Environmental Protection Action Plan 2013–2018 (https://oigusaktid.tallinn.ee/?id=3001&aktid=125983&fd=1&leht=1&q_sort=elex_akt.akt_vkp) with sectoral measures and actions was established for the achievement of the strategy's objectives.

Figure 6.2 shows the projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) for the Tallinn region towards 2100 due to climate change, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005, based on EURO-CORDEX modeling (see also Appendix II).

Figure 6.2 Projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) in the Tallinn region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005.

2. How will demographic changes (e.g. ageing population) influence life in Tallinn?

Currently, male life expectancy at birth in EU Member States is expected to increase by 7.2 years from 77.6 in 2013 to 84.7 in 2060 (Eurostat 2017). As for females, life expectancy at birth is projected to increase by 6.0 years, from 83.1 in 2013 to 89.1 in 2060, implying a convergence of life expectancy between males and females. Despite the variation between EU countries in the absolute levels, all countries show similar trends. As can be seen in Estonia, where females are expected to outlive males by 8.9 years, only Lithuania (10.6 yrs) and Latvia (9.8 yrs) females have higher life expectancy than men in the EU member states (Eurostat 2017).

When comparing the combined life expectancy, Estonia has with 78 years a lower life expectancy than the average of 81.0 years for the EU-28 Member States. In addition to life expectancy, health and wellbeing are important to the quality of life. Older people are more vulnerable for water-related infectious diseases and heat stress in absence of water. Other effects might be a changing frequency of age-related diseases and a changing private/work/care balance for the working population. The shift in age groups might call for different options regarding urban water use, both in terms of availability and water quality.

Tallinn has the lowest proportion of elderly people throughout Estonia. A result of urbanization whereby the young are moving into the suburbs and the older people retire and move to the countryside (Tammaru 2011). Projections for Tallinn show that the city population above 65 years is expected to increase to about 15% by 2030 (see Figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3 Population change per age group in Tallinn, in case of suburbanization scenario 2011-2030, index 2011 = 100% (Tammaru 2011).

3. How will increasing income inequality and waterfront regeneration affect Tallinn?

In the past decade income inequality levels have remained high. Across OECD countries, the average Gini coefficient of the distribution of the disposable household income reached 0.318 in 2013/2014, only marginally higher than in 2007, but the highest value on record since the mid-1980s (OECD 2017). Figure 6.4 shows the Gini coefficient for Estonia, the situation for

Tallinn maybe more favourable due to differences in demography and economy compared to the whole of Estonia.

Given these numbers, it remains important for governments to take into account the inequalities related to access to water for all purposes (including BlueHealth), as well as the quality thereof. The same goes for access to quality and affordable healthcare. Higher inequity in society is correlated with greater social unrest. Access to blue space may be better for high income groups (e.g. higher property values when properties face water (Luttik 2000). In general, income inequality may have a negative effect on environmental quality (Camilo Cardenas, Stranlund et al. 2002, Drabo 2011).

Figure 3. **Estonia lags behind in terms of income inequality and poverty**

Figure 6.4 Income inequality and poverty in Europe (from: OECD Economic Survey Estonia 2017).

Waterfronts in European cities are increasingly redeveloped into attractive blue spaces for citizens, tourist and employees, emphasizing the connection of the city with the water and natural space. Depending on the course of urban developments and decisions made by governments, waterfront regeneration can be more or less inclusive.

Tallinn has several beaches as public bathing areas as well as several business-owned closed areas where public free access to the sea is prevented. However, due to significant increase in the city's building activity near or at the coastal areas, there is a risk that areas that have been in public use until now will be covered in building and lose its function as a public city space (Tallinn environmental strategy 2030).

4. How will (further) digitalisation of society influence life in Tallinn?

The precise directions of further technological progress are unknown, however, it will unmistakably have an impact on our daily life. Our societies are expected to digitalise more than they are now, with developments such as artificial intelligence (including the use of big data), automation, 3D printing, and nanotechnology (Schwab 2017). The Internet of Things (IoT) is an underlying current increasing digital connectivity. It will be easier to transmit and find data for all kinds of purposes, including data for monitoring health and environmental quality. New technologies for smarter urban water systems are expected to be developed (Eurostat 2017), leading to unprecedented possibilities for large-scale environmental surveillance. On the household level, technological systems tailored towards more efficient

domestic water management are expected to be introduced on larger scales. Increased digital connectivity may result in intra-European community building around water, health and well-being. That could potentially lead to increased advocacy and generally, to more inclusiveness. Individuals and organisations will have easier access to data, partly stimulated by a growing health economy, although access to and use of big data might also lead to new societal divisions (McCarthy 2016). Increased public-private partnerships will boost the investment in health and water technology for smart and resilient living environments that are able to promote healthy long living and well-being.

Estonia is one of the frontrunners regarding (application of) digital technological developments, such as internet coverage, speed, digital accessibility of public services etc. Furthermore:

- Technical infrastructure services are of high quality, available for residents of the city and meet the safety and environmental protection requirements.
- The percentage of households using public water supply service from all households was 99% in 2019 and 100% in 2012.
- The municipal authority responsible is the Engineering Services Department.

6.2 BlueHealth ambitions for Tallinn in 2040

During the workshop in Tallinn, the workshop participants identified two **values** as dominant for Tallinn: 'Access for all to blue spaces' and 'Preserving biodiversity'. These values have been used as the basis for the development of the normative views/ambitions for Tallinn in 2040 regarding BlueHealth. The information from the trendscenario (see Chapter 1) was used to identify challenges and opportunities that might be met when realizing these views. Input on interventions was abstracted from the discussion during the workshop.

6.2.1 Access for all to blue spaces: Tallinn as a healthy, blue environment for all

Desired future

In 2040, Tallinn's blue and green spaces are accessible to all residents and tourists. The local government attends to the needs of the inhabitants of the community taking into account their different background and age. These ambitions coincide with the goals laid down in the *Tallinn Environmental Strategy to 2030*, whereby the city is viewed as a living environment for people and the environment and where people have a mutual impact on each other. The protection and improvement of the city's environment is a necessity and a direct obligation as the social and economic development of society depends on it. Current and future generations deserve to live in an environment that promotes physical, mental and social development.

The Tallinn Environmental Strategy 2030 has two objectives for coastal waters:

- The achievement of good conditions for Tallinn's coastal waters, making sure they are as close to natural as possible. A decrease in the pollution load discharged into the sea from the mainland. A decrease of the level of eutrophication of coastal waters.
- City space near the sea is open for all.

Challenges and opportunities on the way to Tallinn's BlueHealth for all

Challenges:

- Currently, the ecological and physical-chemical condition of the largest of Tallinn's inland waterbodies is poor or bad. Caused by nutrients (nitrogen, phosphor) entering into the waterbodies, resulting from the salting of roads, the entry of wastewater into stormwater systems and waterbodies, agricultural diffuse pollution from rural areas, and insufficient performance by water treatment plants in the small settlements and farms in the catchment areas, as well as by the Harku and Vão limestone quarries (Tallinn Environmental Strategy 2030).
- The poor condition of Tallinn's coastal waters due to the high nutrient content and accompanying eutrophication. This problem is common for the Baltic Sea as a whole. The Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region also emphasizes nutrient input, which causes expansion of algal bloom areas, as the main problem associated with the marine environment. In the Bay of Tallinn, the source of problems is coming from rainwater outlets (Tallinn Environmental Strategy 2030).
- The risk of oil and environmental contamination from sea transport and harbours.
- The negative impact of fast ferries on Tallinn's coastal waters and coast.
- The risk of flooding and related risks for the coastal area of Tallinn.
- There is no strategy or development plan that regulates building in Tallinn's coastal waters, along its beaches, shoreline, and coastal areas.

Opportunities:

- (Re)Development of coastal areas can also be used to increase general access to blue spaces. This requires a targeted (investment) plan.
- Lake Ülemiste is now being preserved for drinking water. It could also serve as a blue space for recreation, in such a way that the use does not deteriorate the water quality.
- The extensive coast line around Tallinn could be used to a greater extent for recreation purposes. Accessibility (e.g. better public transport) could then be an option to keep pressure on the environment relatively low.

Interventions contributing to accessibility of blue spaces and health

Interventions coming from multiple policy domains can affect the accessibility of blue spaces, public engagement and impact health directly or indirectly. These interventions for instance, can be related to governance, spatial planning of land and water, community involvement and environmental protection. Within this future scenario for Tallinn, we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to the realization of the ambition to create access for all at blue spaces. Interventions that contribute to inclusiveness have a focus on engaging the local community in planning and ensuring spatial developments that serve different groups in society. Community engagement in spatial planning process would also encourage more focus on the ecological condition of the waterbodies including the aspect of biodiversity protection.

Awareness raising

Raising awareness and expectations of citizens about water bodies and their use, for instance by:

- The promotion and valuation of environmental education in Tallinn, improving the awareness of all of Tallinn's residents in making decisions and taking choices that are related to the environment. These could be related to for instance the importance of biodiversity, its current state, waste disposal at (recreational) water areas and safety measures for bathing.
- Ensuring the sustainability of environmental education. Developing environmental education on all educational levels as well as in adult education.

Cross-sectoral bridging mechanisms

To realise healthy blue spaces for all requires a cross-sectoral approach, for example regarding car use (e.g. investing in public transport or in developing cycling infrastructures), water management (improvement of water quality), public health sector (infrastructures enabling healthy lifestyle), climate resilience programmes (green infrastructure investments) etcetera.

Inclusive urban planning

- Urban planning with a less car-centered approach whereby offices and residential spaces are preferably developed and directed in areas that are located near public transport routes, aiming to minimize the use of cars.

- Project development should take needs of all citizens into account, by preventing the building (private) building/establishments along the water shores which in turn prevent public access to the water (National Spatial Plan Estonia 2030+).

Creating access to green and blue environments

- Providing an network (green-blue) to enable the access and use for those inhabitants, who live in neighbourhood distance from the sea.

6.2.2 Preservation of Tallinn's biodiversity

Desired future

Coastal waterline and the historical downtown are the front piece of Tallinn city. The environment of Tallinn has been valued by its citizens and subjected to sustainable use. A resident of Tallinn appreciates a versatile environment and biodiversity on both a local and a global level, understands the relationships between nature and human activities and acts in a responsible manner. People are aware of the need to save resources and keep the environment clean. There is no need to leave the city to find a green and leafy environment. All age groups can acquire a high-quality environmental education through contemporary environmental education centres.

Tallinn is developing the city as an integral tourism product (City of Tallinn 2008). One of the main activities for achieving the objective is opening the old town and downtown to the sea, creating quality urban space around old town. To expand the attractiveness of the inner city and make the city more enchanting to visitors, preservation of the coastal areas and areas with cultural and environmental values and maintenance of squares and parks including reconstruction of Liberty Square are guaranteed.

The protection of natural diversity, due to human activities and climate change has been ensured through the planning process (City of Tallinn 2011). There is a good overview of biodiversity status and trends in the city. During the drafting of plans, inventories are conducted in order to identify the biodiversity for an area. The plans create the basis for preservation and the improvement of biodiversity. Plans for the restoration and development of the green network are implemented.

Green-blue areas have been valued as an essential component of Tallinn's city environment and city space. When organising city life, which includes planning and construction, green and blue areas are considered as being an element that is even important as the artificial elements of the city environment (buildings, roads, harbor, utility networks). No new areas are being selected for construction activities in green and blue areas. The refurbished areas of the city's space have been maintained.

Several natural streams have been daylighted and restored, which have ecological and climatic functions in addition to providing drainage and the regulation of rain water, enriching the natural environment, ensuring preservation of biodiversity, and being essential from the aesthetic aspect.

Challenges:

- Efficient use of the city space shall be ensured in order to preserve biodiversity and natural diversity in general, while in the longer perspective opportunities shall be created to increase natural diversity in densely built-up areas.
- Raising the citizens' awareness on the importance of biodiversity by adopting and implementing the development plan for the environmental education and in particular in the education centres of the city.
- Balancing the ambitions of biodiversity conservation, urban development and the effects of climate change. Different perspectives (Municipality reports versus stakeholders' perceptions) on current state and trends of biodiversity and challenges that need to be met.
- The increase of emissions due to human activities may lead to (further) pollution of freshwater ecosystems and thus affect biodiversity.
- Tallinn could be framed more as a lake city too, not only a sea city (e.g. Lake Ülemiste). However, public access to blue spaces may cause water pollution.

Opportunities:

- Development of accessible waterfronts, which contributes to an increase of physical, mental, social and economic health. This development also enables the use of public space for restoration of natural areas.
- Development of a cross-sectoral strategic plan for building activities in coastal areas, along the shore, and in coastal sea, enables to cover the issues of environmental and nature protection, the planning and construction of utility networks and the health promotion and recreation.
- The development and management of a green and blue spaces information system, in order to build a detailed overview of public green and blue areas. Issuing passports for green and blue areas, parks and green zones and their entry into the web-based greenery information system.

- Development of user-friendly interfaces for data and information related to urban biodiversity and environment, especially regarding water related health and wellbeing.

Interventions contributing to preservation of Tallinn's biodiversity

Interventions contributing to the preservation of Tallinn's biodiversity come from various policy domains, e.g. related to work, income, housing, urban planning and environmental planning. In this future scenario for Tallinn we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to the preservation of Tallinn's biodiversity. The interventions focus on both awareness raising, stakeholder engagement and physical interventions.

Green capital

It is in the interest of the city to develop the Green Capital idea. To slow down the growth of conventional transport means, alternative ways of movement for citizens and visitors for better air quality and a greener environment.

Waterfront development

To attract tourists and citizens for an active holiday or leisure activities, a reconstruction of daylight hidden streams and reclaim of once-neglected waterfronts in the Tallinn city are necessary, including Härjapea river and connecting water systems of Kadriorg Snell parks, as well as developing public beaches and design and build places for recreation and leisure time in Põhja-Tallinn district and other coastal areas with less developed public access to seafront. Attention should be paid to the urban ecological aspects of the quality of life of its citizens besides economic interests.

Inventory of biota

A biodiversity inventory with an assessment of status and trends of priority species and ecosystems to enable informed planning decisions by city administration as well as encourage the stakeholders engagement and the societal debate. The inventory and assessment should be followed by the city's biodiversity monitoring plan. Development of user-friendly interfaces for biodiversity data and information.

Participatory mapping of green-blue networks and potential conflicts

Mapping green-blue networks using the character of the areas connected and the activities that take place. Determining where there are tensions and conflict areas in the network. Based on this understanding remediation and compensation options can be developed. If possible, this should be carried out within the framework of the thematic plan for the green infrastructure.

Protection plan for Tallinn's water resources

Preservation policies of ecological systems on land, water and wetlands, prevent the deterioration of the waterbodies and related ecosystems. The Development Plan of Tallinn 2009-2027 p. 69 (City of Tallinn 2008), aims to protect ground water as an essential natural resource & protection of town's water bodies and wetlands.

Knowledge gaps that need to be filled

- What waterbodies are necessary for water supply to the administrative territory of Tallinn and what are possible measures for maintaining and improving the water condition.
- What is the influence of waves generated by the hydrofoils as potential hydromorphological pressure factor on ecosystems at sea.

- Organising water environment surveillance and creating a database and making it available for the citizens. Research and surveillance of possible flood risks.
- What ecosystems supporting services would be beneficial for recreation and cultural ecosystem services?
- Define targets to evaluate the interventions to improve and/or adjust to provide a more desired outcome.

6.3 Wrap up BlueHealth Futures for Tallinn

In Tallinn, climate change and its ecological impacts are among the leading trends to influence BlueHealth qualities of city life in Tallinn, mostly related with moderate flooding and heat stress risks. The city has developed local adaptation measures to tackle the effects of climate change and improve the urban biodiversity status.

The loss of biodiversity, pollution and depletion of natural resources have a negative effect for water-related ecosystems, as is the case for the water bodies of Tallinn. By recognizing the essential role of bodies of water (including the sea) as an element of internal structure for the city, the city of Tallinn through its Environmental Strategy 2030, aims to increase the linkage and utilization of banks and bodies of water by creating public points of access to areas that are in open and public use as well as improve the coherence between the green network and residential areas. Departing from current municipal policies, wider development of new open to public waterfronts is foreseeable in the nearest future, which contributes to promotion of citizens' health and wellbeing, enables also to use public space for restoring natural areas and protecting biodiversity.

Tallinn has a relatively young population, stemming from urbanization whereby the young are moving into the suburbs and the older people retire and move to the countryside. This brings different challenges such as the accessibility to the waterfront for the elderly as well as their susceptibility to heat stress in absence of water. Other effects might be a changing frequency of age-related diseases and a changing private/work/care balance for the working population. The shift in age groups might call for different options regarding urban water use, both in terms of availability and water quality.

The increasing income inequality and waterfront regeneration perspectives might affect water related health and wellbeing qualities at a notable rate. Tallinn has several beaches as public bathing areas as well as several business-owned closed areas where public free access to the sea is prevented. However, due to significant increase in the city's building activity near or at the coastal areas, there is a risk that areas that have been in public use until now will be covered in building and lose its function as a public city space.

Estonia being one of the frontrunners regarding (application of) digital technological developments, has a technical infrastructure services of high quality available for residents of the city of Tallinn such as internet coverage, speed, digital accessibility of public services. Ranking among the top ten digital cities in the world, Tallinn aims to use its' technological/digital lead to increase technological systems tailored towards more efficient domestic water management as well as for smarter urban water systems

The precise directions of further technological progress are unknown, however, it will unmistakably have an impact on the daily life. In general, increased digital connectivity may result in enhanced community building around water, health and well-being. That could potentially lead to increased water-and-health advocacy. Individuals will have easier access to

data, although access to and use of big data might also lead to new societal divisions. City authorities and responsible governance sectors together have a key role to facilitate the development of user-friendly interfaces for data and information (related with urban biodiversity and environment, especially regarding water related health and wellbeing).

Additional information:

<https://www.spiegel.de/netzwelt/web/estland-ein-einblick-in-die-start-up-szene-von-tallinn-a-1022184.html>

<https://news.err.ee/100444/it-s-official-tallinn-to-become-eu-s-it-headquarters>

<http://worldpopulationreview.com/world-cities/tallinn-population/>

7 BlueHealth Futures: Trends and ambitions for Thessaloniki

7.1 BlueHealth trends for Thessaloniki

Greece is a country in South Europe and is situated on the Iberian Peninsula (apart from two archipelagoes located in the Mediterranean Sea and Atlantic Ocean, and its African enclaves). Thessaloniki is located on the Thermaic Gulf, at the Northeastern corner of the Aegean Sea and it borders on the west by the Delta of the Axios river. The municipality of Thessaloniki city has a population of 325.000 inhabitants and the Metropolitan Area of Thessaloniki more than one million. The city has an extensive sea front, with a total coastline of about 5.5 km, that is connected with the Port of Thessaloniki, which is the second largest container port in Greece and one of the largest in the Aegean Sea basin, with a total annual traffic capacity of 16 million tones (dry and liquid bulk). The 3.3 km of the Waterfront has been renovated in 2014 by Nikiforidis and Cuomo architects and a total area of 238.800 m² was totally redeveloped with the addition of trees, plants, green spaces, bike roads and playgrounds.

The city is well-known for its cultural life, festivals, the Thessaloniki International Fair (www.helexpo.gr), and the International Thessaloniki Film Festival.

The city climate is directly affected by the sea and lies in a transitional climatic zone with characteristics from several climates. According to Koppen climate classification the city display a humid subtropical climate, with an average of annual precipitation of 450 mm, which drops at 20 to 30 mm during the summer (Beck, Zimmermann et al. 2018). The summer in the city is hot and quite dry with a daily mean temperature of 25.2 °C. In addition, the city displays 32 summer days with a temperature over 32 °C, and during summer months experiences strong heat waves, which is a major problem for specific population groups such as the children and the elderly.

BlueHealth trends for Thessaloniki in 2040

What are relevant trends if we project current developments to the future? What developments will Thessaloniki be facing in the coming decades when it comes to its urban waters and its potential to affect public health and well-being?

Six trends related to these questions, have been assessed as most dominant for Thessaloniki, during an interactive, multidisciplinary stakeholder workshop on September 19th, 2019 in Thessaloniki, with experts and local professionals with backgrounds ranging from the environmental protection and nature conservation, water management, planning and municipality development, public health, social affairs, cultural endowment and community engagement. For this assessment, a longlist of trends was used as an input (Wuijts, De Vries et al. 2019), which was assembled using the DESTEP (demography, economy, social-cultural, technology, ecology and climate, political-institutional) methodology (RIVM 2014). In the Trend scenario for Thessaloniki, we focus upon these six trends, that cover five of the DESTEP categories.

1. *How will climate change and water availability affect the livability of Thessaloniki?*
2. *How will the continued growth of international migration into European countries, affect the livability and social coherence of Thessaloniki?*
3. *Will new technology create solutions for more healthy urban living in the city?*
4. *What could the potential increase of recreational use of blue spaces imply for Thessaloniki?*
5. *How will developments towards more healthy urban living in EU policies and strategies affect local decision-making within the domains of water and health in Thessaloniki?*
6. *What could changes in labour conditions imply for the use of blue spaces?*

Description of trends for Thessaloniki

1. *How will climate change and water availability affect the livability of Thessaloniki?*

Even with major mitigation efforts, the IPCC has projected a tendency towards further global warming in the 21st century. As a result, the amount of snow and ice will diminish, and heat waves, (extreme) droughts, and floods will occur more frequently (Della-Marta, Haylock et al.

2007, Della-Marta, Luterbacher et al. 2007, Perkins and Alexander 2012, Perkins, Alexander et al. 2012, IPCC 2014, Zampieri, Russo et al. 2016). This will affect water availability and water quality and related waterborne and vector-borne infectious diseases (Delpha, Jung et al. 2009, Whitehead, Wilby et al. 2009, EEA 2017). More heat stress and related health effects - especially in urban areas - may occur if no adaptation measures are implemented (Kleerekoper, Van Esch et al. 2012, EEA 2017, Scoccimarro, Fogli et al. 2017). Especially in Southern Europe, fresh water is scarce in summers (EC 2013) and the demands of multiple users increases in these periods (e.g. agriculture, cooling water, bathing water, drinking water). This may lead to further water quality deterioration, higher water temperatures, and the intrusion of salt-water into aquifers and agricultural land due to depletion of natural resources as is already ongoing (EEA 2008, Foster and Custodio 2019).

Increased river flows during winter and lower river flows during summer have been recorded since the 1960s in large parts of Europe (EC 2013). It is also projected to result in strong changes of river flows and their extremes across Europe. The Urban Heat Island effect and sea level rise are expected to be the major effects of climate change for the city of Thessaloniki (YPEHODE 2002, Yiannakou and Salata 2017). The major rivers that flow next or through Thessaloniki area are the Axios river, the Gallikos river, the Loudias river and the Aliakmon river which is the largest river in Greece. One of the few positive effects of climate change is the revival of the Gallikos river due to Aliakmon, cause large quantities of water, intended to supply the urban complex of Thessaloniki were superfluous and therefore driven towards the riverbed of the Gallikos (Karageorgis and et al. 2005). In the future, special attention should be taken concerning the protection and the preservation of the delta's of Aliakmon and Axios which is known for the thousands of ducks they host, mainly during winter months (Poulos, Chronis et al. 2000).

Figure 7.1 shows the projected change of the number of summer days ($> 25^{\circ}\text{C}$) for the Thessaloniki region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005, based on EURO-CORDEX modelling (see Annex II). The number of summer days is expected to rise with 20 to 40 days. It should be noted that for the Thessaloniki region, EURO-CORDEX models tend to overestimate by about 20%.

The climate in Thessaloniki is Mediterranean, with cold and wet winters and hot and dry summers. As a result of climate change, temperature has been rising since the 1950s by 1°C (Hellenic National Meteorological Service, <http://www.emy.gr/emv/en/>). Together with the expected increase in extreme climatic events, such as heat waves, the Urban Heat Island Effect is likely to increase in intensity (Gill, Handley et al. 2007, Dugord, Lauf et al. 2014). Studies have shown that Thessaloniki has become more arid and that, while the annual rainfall levels are significantly lower, rainfall itself has become heavier, which means an increased risk of flash floods. Thessaloniki also exhibits high humidity levels, which have increased in recent years (Yiannakou and Salata 2017).

Figure 7.1 Projected change of the number of summer days (> 25 °C) in the Thessaloniki region towards 2100, compared to the timeframe 1986-2005.

2. *How will the continued growth of international migration into European countries, affect the livability and social coherence of Thessaloniki?*

Migration flows across the world have increased in recent decades. This trend is likely to persist and even intensify, since the structural factors that drive migration will not easily reverse. The main drivers for migration are economic inequalities, demographic imbalances, conflicts, disasters, and the impacts of climate and other environmental changes (UN 2017). Droughts and water scarcity can directly and indirectly (exacerbating conflict and socio-economic inequalities) drive migration (Jägerskog, Engstrand-Neacsu et al. 2016). Migration in the EU consists both of citizens from EU-Member States moving to other EU-Member States, and migration from and to non-EU countries. In 2015, 4.7 million people immigrated to one of the EU-28 Member States. About 2.7 million of these immigrants came to the EU-28 from non-member countries. In addition, 1.9 million people previously residing in one EU Member State migrated to another Member State (Eurostat 2017). In the past decades, Europe has been one of the net receivers of international migrants (Eurostat 2017). There were 34.3 million people born outside of the EU-28 living in an EU Member State on January 1st 2015, while there were 18.5 million persons who had been born in a different EU Member State from the one where they were resident (Eurostat 2017). Emigration from the EU consisted of at least 2.8 million emigrants that have left an EU Member State in 2015 (Eurostat 2017).

In general, health problems of refugees and migrants are similar to those of the rest of the population, although some groups may experience a higher prevalence of certain diseases (see for example Montesi, Caletti et al. (2016)). The WHO (2017) and Rechel, Mladovsky et al. (2011) describe how vulnerable migrants face acute problems, such as mental health

problems and physical threats due to living under poor circumstances, exhaustion, and violence. There is strong evidence that access to health services remains problematic for migrants in most EU countries (Rechel, Mladovsky et al. 2011). Risks related to urban water, may therefore have more impact on some vulnerable groups. In general, children are more at risk for most of the water-related risks.

Currently, 6.2 % of the population in Thessaloniki has a foreign nationality. The issue of gentrification in different parts of the city has been identified as a potential risk for urban cohesion. The vast majority of the prefecture's (Central Macedonia) 112,000-strong migrant population (more than 90%) live in Greater Thessaloniki, 82% of them in the Conurbation. The highest concentration is in the Peri-Urban Zone, whereby their share in the population approaches 12%. The largest groups are Albanians (25.1%) and Georgians (13.1%), followed by Russians, Armenians, Cypriots (to a large extent possibly students), Armenians and Bulgarians. Soviet Greeks altogether form the most numerous group, with a 28.7% share among all migrants, but they remain a diverse community in terms of origin (coming mostly from Georgia and Russia, and to a lesser extent Armenia and the Ukraine, as well as Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan). Most the migrants are employed in low-skilled positions such as domestic workers, manual laborers, and assistants in retail stores (Pratsinakis 2005) (Pratsinakis, 2005). Other ethnic-groups such as the Chinese and the Western-country nationals are mainly self-employed. More than 90% of city migrants are located in the western districts where the house rents are reduced compared to the city center and the eastern part (Katsavouniotou and Kourti, 2008). There is a lack of information concerning the socio-economic status of the Middle-Eastern immigrants arrived in Thessaloniki at the period 2015-2019 but in a recent country-wide research showed that 58% of the national Greeks believe that Middle-Eastern immigrants are a threat for the Greek culture and identity, 56% believe that their impact in the Greek economy is negative and, finally 53% believe that due to their presence the criminality has been enhanced (DiaNEOsis and Hanns Seidel Institute, 2019). The latter sets major problems for the Greek society and the integration of the recent arrived immigrants in Thessaloniki.

3. Will new technology create solutions for more healthy urban living in the city?

The trend towards healthier urban living environments is further stimulated by digitalisation. Increased environmental surveillance through small-scale sensors and environmental quality forecasting enhances the ambition for clean urban environments. That is, exposure to contaminants is minimal, the opportunities for physical exercise and mental relaxing are high. Digitalisation may stimulate the development of smart urban water management, including smart climate resilient water management like efficient use of water storage capacity and the use of storm water overflows. This will affect the quality of the living environment (both built and natural), water availability, and the acceleration towards a climate resilient infrastructure (Sedlak 2015). With management of big data, governments will have more opportunities to manage urban transportation, water and energy resources, and waste efficiently (OECD 2016). Large scale implementation of decentralised wastewater systems that are possibly more efficient, could affect performance and management of centralised sewer systems to a large extent, although progress towards adoption and implementation of these decentralised systems is slow. Key barriers reported in literature include investments, organisational challenges, and the absence of a prohibitive regulatory framework (e.g., (Spiller and Zeeman 2013, Guimarães, Malheiros et al. 2016)).

4. What could the potential increase of recreational use of blue spaces imply for Thessaloniki?

Worldwide, the popularity of recreational activities has grown. This includes water related activities, for example in both inland and marine waters. Moreover, the ease of travel has altered the public use of water for recreational purposes (WHO 2005). Developments in technologies such as wetsuit design and water sports equipment (e.g. stand-up paddle boards) have added upon that. Nearly 70% of

European tourists spend their holidays at a waterside location, mostly within other European countries, with around two billion days spent annually at coastal recreational resorts (EU 2015, ETA 2016). The World Tourism Organization predicts that by 2026, 346 million tourists will visit Mediterranean destinations annually, representing about 22% of all arrivals worldwide (UNWTO 2018). Greece ended 2018 with a new historical record for tourism, as 33 million international tourists made their way through the country and revenues in the sector surpassed 16 billion euros (UNWTO 2018). Thus, an increase of tourism is being expected for Greece by 2026.

5. *How will developments towards more healthy urban living in EU policies and strategies affect local decision-making within the domains of water and health in Thessaloniki?*

Although the EU has no formal authority over urban policy, cities play a major role in implementing EU policy. The EU's general environmental legislation aims to make sure cities have clean air and water, that the natural environment and biodiversity is protected, that cities deal properly with waste, and that green infrastructure is promoted. The EU has recognised the challenges European cities face in the upcoming years (e.g. ageing of its population, migration, and effects of climate change), but also identify cities as both the source and solution of economic, environmental and social challenges. The EU has therefore set targets for 2020 to achieve smart, sustainable and inclusive growth (EU Urban Agenda (EC 2016)). Healthy urban environments are part of this agenda (although public health is not explicitly mentioned), and are also part of the 7th Environment Action Programme (2014-2020) and the Urban Audit Programme. Furthermore, the EU 3rd Health Programme (2014-2020) (EC 2014) aims to foster supportive environments for healthy lifestyles. Thessaloniki joined the EU Covenant of Mayors initiative to increase energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources in 2011 and in 2017 the EU Urban Water Agenda 2030.

6. *What could changes in labour conditions imply for the use of blue spaces?*

There is an increasing amount of European workers with only a part-time job, but with a **clear East-West divide between countries**: in Central and Eastern European countries part-time work remains a marginal phenomenon even among women, while the Western countries have embraced it much more widely (Vaalavuo 2016). According to the data available from the Greek Government, the economic crisis changed the rate, profile and origination of the inflow of migrant workers in Greece. Nevertheless, even today, a large number of migrant workers is entering the country illegally and seek employment which usually is in the form of unregistered, low skilled, low paid and on temporary basis. Most of them are willing to get any job and even work as unskilled personnel to jobs which are not related to their profession or qualifications (Demoussis and al. 2010). The latter denotes that in Greece there is a blurred image on the working conditions of immigrants as most of them are employed in seasonal jobs such as tourism, services and household jobs.

Issues relating to the future job market in Europe include the rise of independent and alternative working arrangements such as the shortening of workweeks (currently Greece has a 43 hours workweek), flexibility of contracts, working hours, and the location of work (ESPC 2016). There is an increasing focus on a healthy work-life balance. Traditional workweeks of 40 hours (or more) may no longer be standard now that worker preferences lay in reducing the weekly working time by several hours. Countries are regulating working time by introducing new legislation (Eurofound and ILO 2017).

7.2 BlueHealth ambitions for Thessaloniki in 2040

During the stakeholder workshop, two values were identified as dominant for Thessaloniki: sustainable urban design and health for all (promoting social equity). These values have been used as the basis for normative views on Thessaloniki in 2040 regarding BlueHealth. The information from the Trendscenario was used to identify challenges and opportunities that arise from these trends and what should be done to realize these views. Input on interventions was abstracted from the discussion during the workshop. These two values, the underlying trends and possibilities to achieve a more desirable future have been assimilated into two storylines: 'Sustainable urban design' and 'A healthy, socially fair and safe Thessaloniki'.

7.2.1 'Sustainable urban design'

Desired future

The city of Thessaloniki is an example of sustainable urban design by 2040. Respecting its ancient cultural monuments, the city proactively deals with the challenges set by climate change and has used the interventions needed to develop itself towards an attractive residences for all its citizens. With the prospects of rising temperatures and more extremes in rainfall and periods of drought, meeting the

demand for water and providing clean and good quality water are important challenges. In 2040 there is a sufficient supply of clean drinking water, and the available water in the city is used efficiently (introduction of water meters). Green spaces along the renovated waterfront allow people to enjoy life outdoors longer during hot days. The water quality of the Gulf of Thessaloniki has improved and allows multiple use for water related activities.

Challenges and opportunities on the way to sustainable urban design

Challenges:

- The effects of climate change will become significant towards the end of the 21st century and thus beyond the timescale of this scenario (2040) (Rajczak and Schär 2017). Even so, extreme weather events (heavy rainfall, mainly in winter, heat waves and periods of drought) will occur more frequently in the coming decades in the Thessaloniki region (Yiannakou and Salata 2017).
- Climate resilience calls for measures to adapt for water excess and water shortages, and related issues towards water quality. Due to the long lifetimes of urban infrastructure, effects beyond 2040 need to be counted for in current long-term urban planning as well and clean drinking water needs to be available to all citizens. The likely effects of climate change on the water resources of the eastern Mediterranean and Middle East region have been investigated using a high-resolution regional climate model (PRECIS) by comparing precipitation simulations of 2040-2069 and 2070-2099 with 1961-1990 (Chenoweth and al. 2011). The projected change in internal water resources is assumed to be the same as the projected change in precipitation. Greece is expected to have an 18% precipitation decrease by midcentury, and 22% by the end of the century. The population is expected to decline in a modest rate so Greece's per capita water resources are expected to decline but still remains high compared to neighboring countries. For the latter reasons measures such as constructing additional water supply infrastructures, improve data collection and improve water storage conditions needs to be taken.

- Long periods of high temperatures and drought may lead to increased algae blooms and the development of water quality problems due to ongoing inputs from various activities.
- Investments in good quality of surface waters and accessibility attribute to the attractiveness of the city to live in, but could also attribute to more gentrification and widen the social gap.
- The water quality of the Gulf of Thessaloniki ('Thermaikos') is such that it limits current use for water related activities like bathing or other water sports alongside the urban waterfront.
- The multiple use of space (cars, bicycles, pedestrians) along the waterfront in Thessaloniki, challenges the realisation of healthy blue/green spaces.
- The allocation of roles, responsibilities and means for the waterfront area is unclear and hampers a sustainable conservation of the renovated waterfront. For instance, extreme weather events in the past have resulted in trees cut off, traffic disrupted and no structure to cope with it.
- The effects of atmospheric pollution on blue health in cities are not yet known and currently there is ongoing research on the differential immunological effects between office workers and people who visit the coastline in their daily routine. In addition, in coastal cities such as Thessaloniki, future research should focus on the combinational effect of the coastal urban emissions, the ship emissions from the close located to the city center port and the sea emissions.

Opportunities:

- Increasing the surface of blue and green spaces in the city to retain water and form a source of cooling and shade during warm periods in summer (nature-based solutions). For instance the Thermi Dam can be turned into a green hub and impact the lives and health of citizens in the nearby area in a positive way.

- Informing the general public and raising awareness on the importance of efficient water use, especially in periods of droughts, by the introduction of water meters and targeted information during heat waves.
- Use projects that aim to increase climate resilience to create co-benefits for healthy urban blue/green spaces. For instance to utilize riverfront development Axios for public recreation or create more green areas with natural shade near the seaside so people can stay longer outside during daytime.
- The development of waterfront activities in the city centre (e.g. harbour for small yachts) could contribute to the economy of the area and open up to its citizens.

Interventions contributing to sustainable urban design

Interventions in multiple policy domains, e.g. related to work, income, housing, transport, can affect sustainability, climate resilience and health directly or indirectly. This especially holds in urban environments with a high density of activities and usages of space and complex social interactions. Within this future scenario for Thessaloniki we focus on possible interventions that directly contribute to climate resilient, sustainable urban design and health. Instruments to adapt the outdoor environment to the effects of climate change in ways that are beneficial to health generally include interventions in blue and green spaces, like water squares or playgrounds. Other types of interventions focus on raising awareness among citizens and companies, effectiveness of governance arrangements and robust and healthy urban design.

Adapting the built environment to adapt to climate change

Both buildings and public spaces should be adapted to the changing climate in order to become more resilient. Greening public space can lead to several benefits for public health and climate resilience. More green space, including vertical planting and green roofs and attractive, accessible blue spaces can contribute to people's mental health and wellbeing, they can provide shade and cooling during warm periods in summer (reducing the urban heat island effect) and retain water in periods of heavy rainfall (nature based solutions) (Naturvation 2019). Climate proof-building is another way to creating a more climate resilient city. For example, by installing carbon-efficient warming and cooling

techniques instead of using air-conditioning or electric heating. The project 'Bioclimatic upgrade of public spaces' in the historic city centre is a good example of how to adapt to climate change and reduce the urban heat island effect, e.g. by the use of street vans.

A heat protocol

A heat protocol was set up recently to raise awareness among citizens on how to act during heatwaves, as the city experiences 32 days over 32 °C per year and the number of these days is expected to rise due to climate change (Antzoulatos and al. 2019). The protocol has been developed in the context of another EU project called BEAWARE, which goal is to provide early warnings, risk assessment and decision support to stakeholders and public authorities, on management of natural disasters (Antzoulatos and al. 2019). The latter system integrates information from weather data received from the weather public service, drones, social media, sensors and mobile applications to a single database, and then sends the appropriate warnings to municipalities or the central administration depending on the risk and danger classification. Concerning heatwaves the final goal of the system is to provide accurate predictions of the upcoming raise of the temperature and inform the general public through social media, bus stops or public billboards signs. Thus, all the vulnerable age-groups such as children and the elderly can take the appropriate precautions.

Monitoring and communication

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and develop an adaptation strategy in case measures do not lead to the expected result. Model results need to be transformed into understandable information for citizens.

Improving the treatment, reduction of overflows and reuse of waste water

Water saving and water reuse initiatives could offer a positive contribution to deal with water scarcity. A good example is the Waste Water Treatment Plant (WWTP) of Thessaloniki that is used for agricultural irrigation after mixing with freshwater at a 1:5 ratio. The main crops irrigated are rice, corn and alfalfa, with an irrigated area of 2,500 ha.

The increase of extreme rainfall events due to climate change could result in more overflows of untreated sewage water into the Thermaikos Gulf. Initiatives that entail a reduced emission of effluent, including the reduction of overflows, to the surface water also contribute to chemical and ecological water quality improvement and the use of these waters for health (Jensen, Lauridsen et al. 2015).

Improve sea transport, through small ship of maximum capacity of 200 people

There is an existing commute network to connect the centre to the eastern part of Thessaloniki (Kalamaria, Angelohori) but only for touristic reasons and it would be a good opportunity to upgrade the marine transportation to an effective daily alternative transportation from the eastern and the western to the city center. The development of a Maritime Public Transport System in the Thermaikos Gulf is current in the schedule of the Public Thessaloniki Transportation Authority, in a similar system such as the maritime transport in Sydney, Boston and Istanbul (Petrakis and colleagues 2014) et al., 2014).

Clean shipping for clean air and healthy oceans

To keep the port, its surroundings and the sea clean, policies could be developed to admit cleaner and more sustainable ships to the port, by using the [clean shipping index](#). For example by reduced port fees for clean shipping.

Competitive design for innovations

More green parks within the urban environment and close to the waterfront. Vegetation can be a powerful tool in the fight against excessive city heat. Not only does greenery provide shade, it stimulates evapotranspiration, the process by which water evaporating from plants' leaves reduces the adjacent air temperature. When the population grows and buildings got taller, the focus could be to include [skyrise greenery](#): vertical planting and green roofs.

Awareness raising

Increase awareness for sustainable behavior, especially at the municipality level, where Greece is trying to catch up with other European countries. Till recent years, the country has been fined due to lack of sanitary landfills (Ezeah et al., 2014). Over the recent years the situation is much better and the goal for 2020 is to reduce the amount of waste send to landfills at least 35%. In addition, municipalities

needs to take action for a greater citizen participation in recycling to meet the 50% recycling target set by the Revised Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC), e.g. regarding plastic waste.

Resilient housing

Materials for buildings (inside and outside) are suitable for climate change. Both buildings and public spaces should be adapted to the changing climate in order to become more resilient. Climate proof-building is another way to creating a more climate resilient city. For example, by installing carbon-efficient warming and cooling techniques instead of using air-conditioning or electric heating.

7.2.2 'Health for all in Thessaloniki'

Desired future

In 2040 Thessaloniki is a healthy city, where active living is promoted, where all can breathe clean air and enjoy quality public spaces to spend time with friends and relatives, and people's health and well-being is guaranteed. Clean and healthy drinking water is a commodity for all. Thessaloniki generates accessible blue spaces that are suitable for everyone to recreate.

Challenges and opportunities on the way to health for all in Thessaloniki

Challenges:

- Wealth and health disparities between neighborhoods are unequally distributed. More vulnerable people and poorer neighbourhoods will likely be more affected by the climate change, e.g. due to the urban heat island effect and other extreme weather events. This might lead to an increase in the vulnerable population threatened by energy poverty, health problems and the rising cost of living due to climate change. In addition, more income inequality will likely create more health inequalities too. Due to more heat waves and increased humidity levels, the presence of mosquitos might increase as well, affecting vulnerable groups the most. Excess heat, cold and flooding may result in chaos in the city and more demands to crisis management by the municipality.
- Accessibility and resilience of housing for residents in lower income groups and, especially for elderly housing that is suited to their needs. Installations and pumps are needed to make buildings adaptive (no heating or drinking water facilities in some old buildings).
- Equal access to blue and green spaces in and close to the city.
- Different groups use (blue) public space in different, sometimes conflicting ways.

Opportunities:

- The long waterfront offers great potential to develop healthy blue and green spaces. Consider the impact of healthy blue spaces with others who use the waterfront to promote its use in this way.
- The role of volunteers so far was very important in keeping the waterfront clean. This strong role could be used more structurally, in both development and preservation of blue and green spaces.
- Include perceptions, needs and ideas of different stakeholders, especially neighbourhood residents in plans for creating more blue and green spaces within the city.

Interventions contributing to health for all in Thessaloniki

Urban waterfront

With the realisation of Europe's longest waterfront, Thessaloniki has created opportunities for physical exercise and places to relax and enjoy the sea (<https://www.citylab.com/design/2019/07/thessaloniki-greece-new-waterfront-park-redevelopment-europe/593479/>). However, the options for water activities near the city centre, are limited now, due to shipping and water quality issues.

More water activities for all

More exercise is good for health. In this way, more water activities can also contribute to people's health and also provide cooling at warmer days. Swimming is one of the water activities at warm days but is also risk because of droughting. Swimming lessons at school will contribute to the safety of all children of the city.

More free transportation to go bathing

The beaches of Thessaloniki are far from the city centre. To give everyone access to the beaches, free transportation would benefit the health of the residents. In this matter it will help the general redevelopment of the public transportation system in Thessaloniki. Starting from 2020, twelve measures are about to be taken in order to upgrade the transportation for the citizens. These measures include new bus lanes, development of bike roads, bike sharing system, restructuring of bus stops, limitation of roadside parking, new pedestrian facilities, and public space regeneration, and maritime transportation (Petrakis and colleagues 2014).

Ventilation and evaporation in streets for cooling

During the day, buildings heat up in the sun. Because of this, the temperature can stay considerably high at night. People sleep bad because of this, which has an effect on their health. Water has been used for ages as a means for cooling. Fountains for instance, stimulate the evaporation of water and cool the hot, dry city air. Cool sea wind can be used as a ventilation system in the streets. The evaporation and shadow of the trees can contribute to cooling as well.

Heat maps alert for vulnerable groups

The information provided by the heat protocol can be used to inform the general public through social media, bus stops or public billboards signs. Thus, all the vulnerable age-groups such as children and the elderly can take the appropriate precautions.

Access to tap water for all

With the increase in heat waves, the demand for free tap water points will increase. Most places in Europe do have drinkable tap water, which means you'll save money filling a reusable water bottle up before heading out. Some countries, like Italy, Germany, and Belgium, have public taps in the streets where you can refill for free.

Improve awareness and interaction

Evidence based, transparent and understandable data helps to raise awareness among the general public on the value of blue spaces for health. It is important that these communication and engagement practices address different age groups, gender and cultural diverse groups in multi languages and anticipate on the different users of blue spaces (children facilities, sports, bicycling, elderly, open plains, no lanes, accessibility for all).

Monitoring and communication, more crisis management more information

Engagement and acceptance of stakeholders increases if there is information on the actual contribution of measures to resilience (Blackstock, Waylen et al. 2012). It is therefore important to develop indicators for monitoring, communication and, in case measures do not lead to expected results, also develop an adaptation strategy (see also paragraph on heat protocol, p. 13).

Involvement of local community

Involvement of the local community to get a better understanding of local needs, to use local knowledge on what works and what doesn't (local community process with combination of people that have a lot of knowledge and less knowledge) and to promote participation for decision making.

Creating accessible public green and blue spaces for all so different activities can take place

Greening public space can lead to several benefits for public health and climate resilience. More green space and attractive, accessible blue spaces can contribute to people's mental health and wellbeing, they can provide shade and cooling during warm periods in summer (reducing the urban heat island effect) and retain water in periods of heavy rainfall (nature based solutions) (Naturvation 2019). Introducing green roofs might be a good strategy to increase green spaces in cities with pressure on space. Green roofs could help mitigate the effects of climate change by improving building insulation, increasing biodiversity, and improving rainwater management. It also stimulates local food production and creates a recreation and meeting area for building inhabitants that can contribute to social interaction among neighbours, like for instance the example from City of Barcelona (2013).

7.3 Wrap up BlueHealth Futures for Thessaloniki

Several issues concerning the impact of the climate change appeared to be relevant in the city of Thessaloniki. The sea level rise is expected to have impact on the city of Thessaloniki, because of the increased risk of flooding of waterfronts. A positive effect of climate change is the large quantities of water cause a revival of the Gallikos river and the superfluous water – after supplying the urban complex of Thessaloniki – could be led into the Aliakmon delta. Both the Aliakmon and Axios delta deserve special attention in protection and the preservation, as they are known to host thousands of ducks, mainly during winter months.

Another relevant impact of climate change in Thessaloniki concerns the urban heat island effect. With the increase in heat waves, the demand for free tap water points will increase, so it would be effective for the city to create more places with access to high-quality tap water for its citizens. In addition, the use of cool sea wind as a ventilation system in the streets, and the shadow of the trees as cooling system should become a major priority. Also, a heat map alert should be created in order to protect the vulnerable groups from heat waves. Finally, water activities could also provide cooling at warmer days, such as swimming, which is an activity that increases the potential risk of drowning. Thus, swimming lessons at school and the presence of lifeguards at the nearby beaches are important to secure the safety among bathing children.

Since nearly 70% of European tourists spend their holidays at a waterside location, Thessaloniki should grab the opportunity and increase the use of blue spaces in the future. The long waterfront offers great potential to develop healthy blue and green spaces. Stakeholder engagement and acceptance could increase the insights into needs and ideas on the contribution of measures to resilience, especially when coming from neighbourhood residents contributing to plans for creating more blue and green spaces within the city.

In addition, digitalisation may stimulate the development of smart urban water management, including smart climate resilient water management. Big data management, and Internet of Things will have a major role for the development of a blue space-friendly environment for the tourists and the residents of the city, concerning the management of urban transportation, water and energy resources, wastes and weather information. As the beaches of Thessaloniki are far from the centre, free transportation measures should be taken into consideration, in order to provide access to the beaches to everyone. This is even more important than the issue of gentrification, that has been identified as a potential risk for urban cohesion in different parts of the city. Currently, 6.2% of the population in Thessaloniki has a foreign nationality, the majority being located in the Western districts. Moreover, due to the vast arrival of immigrants in 2018-2019, socio-economic information on newly arrived Middle-Eastern immigrants is lacking, and thus, it is more difficult to integrate them in the local society. There is a need to set up first-encounter facilities where the immigrants and the refugees will be assessed concerning their background in order to use their skills in relevant jobs or send their children to suitable schools.

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Annex I BlueHealth City Profile Amsterdam (workshop material)

City profile AMSTERDAM

Demography

- 835.000 inhabitants (2016)
- Population growth due to natural increase and migration
- 450.000 households; more than 50% single households
- largest age group is 20-35, slowly ageing population

Technology

- Sanitation 100 %
- Rain/water/Sewage spills remediated
- Local water reuse initiatives

Economy

- Growth rate of 3% (national 2%)
- Most of the employees work in highly specialized, high skilled jobs or lower skilled jobs. About 8 percent is unemployed.
- Important economic activities: services, industries, tourism, research, harbour
- Main mode of transport:
 - 25% (2% hybrid, 1% electric)
 - 32%

Ecology & Climate

- 4,8 % of total energy consumption is from a sustainable source
- the number of species of wild bees has risen with 20%
- In some parts of the city biodiversity is declining
- Weather patterns will change: rising temperatures, drier summers and warmer winters, more extremes, urban flooding versus water scarcity

Social-cultural

- Half of the city's population has a migration background
- 12,5% of the population has a foreign nationality (167 different nationalities)

Bevolking naar herkomstgroepering, 1990-2040

Source: CBS, prognose 2015

Political-Institutional

- Governance performance varies from overall encouraging for flooding, moderate for water scarcity to limited for governance of the urban heat island effect.
- Water governance is divided over national, regional, municipal and district councils

Source: waterthuis.nl/2015

Spatial

- Old industrial harbor sites are being transformed into areas for residential, recreational, cultural use, services industries.
- Waterways within the city is used for transport, tourism, recreation and living on house boats.

11-05-2017
Susanne Wuijts, Marit de Vries and Liesbet O'Brien - van Dreehem

Annex II Methodology used for projections of warm days

Four Regional Climate models taking part to the EURO-CORDEX (Jacob et al. 2014) EUR11 effort (about 12 km as horizontal resolution) have been used to compute anomalies

of summer days number with respect to the historical period. Daily data of maximum temperature over a 3x3 grid box (about 35x35 km²) around Amsterdam are used for the definitions of the summer day number in each year.

Figure shows averaged anomalies over a 20-y time window compared to the historical 1986-2005 period.

Two future scenarios are considered: the Representative concentration Pathways leading to a radiative forcing increase of 8.5 W/m² (RCP8.5) and 4.5 W/m² (RCP4.5)

with respect to the preindustrial level (van Vuuren et al. 2011).

The RCP8.5 combines assumptions about high population and relatively slow income growth with modest rates of technological change and energy intensity improvements,

leading in the long term to high energy demand and GHG emissions in absence of climate change policies (Riahi et al. 2011).

RCP8.5 thus corresponds to the pathway with the highest greenhouse gas emissions within the RCPs considered by the fifth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5, Taylor et al. 2012).

On the other hand RCP4.5 (Thomson et al. 2011) is a stabilization scenario and assumes that climate policies,

in this instance the introduction of a set of global greenhouse gas emissions prices, are invoked to achieve the goal of limiting emissions and radiative forcing.

Thus RCP4.5 corresponds to a more moderate scenario compared to RCP8.5.

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Annex III BlueHealth City Profile Barcelona (workshop material)

City profile Barcelona

Demography

- 1.620.809 inhabitants (2017)
- High population density (15.873 hab/km²)
- 658.375 households; 31% one person, 58% couples, 11% father or mother with children (2017)
- Largest age group is 35-39, with aging population. Population aged between 15—44 has been reduced 10% in the last 10 years.

Economy

- Estimated Gross Domestic Product of 3,3 (2017)
- Most of the employees work in the service sector followed by the commercial sector. Tourism is a big contributor to economy (including transatlantic ships and flights).
- Unemployment rate from 10.5 to 11.3% for men and from 9.6 to 12.8% for women during 2017.
- Increase of unemployed population that is not receiving any kind of economic benefit.
- Occupation rate increased, partly due to a decreasing active population.
- Private car and motorbike represent 40% of the daily trips in Barcelona. Cycling is less than 2%.
- 14.5 million trips on the Bike sharing system (2018)

Social-cultural

- 17.6% of the city population born outside Spain (2017)
- 41 different nationalities (of >1000 residents)
- Population from China, Italy and Russia have increased the most (in absolute terms)
- In 2015 life expectancy was 80.8 years for men and 86.6 years for women; it differs depending on the neighborhood.

Population trend by nationality

■ Spanish ■ Other EU ■ Other European ■ Africa ■ North and Central America ■ South America ■ Asia and Oceania

Technology

- Sanitation 98%
- water supply: demand threatens supplies
- water quality: wastewater is untreated for 1 million people in region.
- Problems with high levels of Pb due to old pipework
- 20% of phreatic water is used for municipal services (the city holds an aquifer)
- Flood control: most of main fluvial networks are channelized. Increasing importance of flooding by secondary, ephemeral streams and precipitation

Ecology & Climate

- The city is situated next to the sea and lies between two rivers, a natural park and a mountain. The presence of the sea and the topography makes the city specially vulnerable for the heat island and thermal inversion effects.
- 2 % of total energy consumption is from a sustainable source (2016)
- Weather patterns will change: rising temperatures, drier summers and higher variability for spring/ autumn (desertification of the Mediterranean area). Higher frequency of extreme events.

Political-Institutional

- Water in the Metropolitan Region is provided by a variety of companies (public, semi-public and private).
- Local, supra-local and regional institutions are in charge sewers, flood control works and wastewater treatment facilities. Part of the costs are financed through taxes included in the water bills. This makes the city the most expensive in the country for these activities.

Spatial

- Implementation of superblocks: mini neighbourhoods around which traffic flows, and where spaces are repurposed. The aim is to create community spaces and to reduce traffic, air pollution and noise.
- Increase of housing prices due to gentrification
- Urban beaches attract many people, mainly tourists
- High and worsening air pollution, partly due to increase in urban mobility and economic activity.

23-8-2019
Globe Canvas, Markt der Visionen und Lebensformen - von Reizen

Annex IV BlueHealth city profile Plymouth (workshop material)

City profile PLYMOUTH

Demography

- 264,000 inhabitants (2016).
- Little migration in terms of net international (+0.45%) or net internal (-0.15%) from 2015 to 2016.

Technology

- The new £60million Mayflower Water Treatment Works is near completion (the first of its kind in the UK) and will produce high quality tap water for all of Plymouth.
- The University of Plymouth's Marine Institute hosts advanced technological facilities in marine engineering and biogeochemistry.

Economy

- The average Plymouth resident has approximately £16,000 of disposable income (i.e. after compulsory tax deductions), the second lowest in the South-West (2015).
- 139,000 people are economically active, with 7,000 unemployed.
- Devonport Naval Base generates around 10% of Plymouth's income, employing 2,500 service personnel and civilians.

Ecology & Climate

- Annually, the average household consumes 3,500 kilowatt-hours of electricity, in the lowest 20% of local authorities in the country (2016).
- In 2012 a target of reducing carbon emissions by a minimum of 35% by 2020 was set.
- Plymouth's low carbon sector's productivity had lagged behind the UK average but is predicted to outstrip growth in other industries by 2020, creating 880 new jobs in the process.

Social-cultural

- 6% of Plymouth residents are non-British.
- In the last census, 58% report being Christian, 33% of no religion, and 1.9% other religions.
- Plymouth was rebranded "Britain's Ocean City" in 2013 and will host Mayflower 400 events in 2020, celebrating 400 years since the sailing of the Mayflower.
- If Sutton Harbour Holdings takeover bid is successful, a block of flats, shops, and restaurants at East Quay will be developed as soon as possible.
- Plymouth Fisheries has also received attention for potential development as a restaurant-led tourist destination.

Political-Institutional

- Plymouth residents benefit from the government's £50 contribution towards water bills - allegedly a reward for the work done to protect the region's bathing waters.
- An ongoing dispute is preventing the repair of the Sutton Harbour footbridge, limiting access between the Barbican and Coxside.
- The Ministry of Defence have confirmed that all Plymouth-based naval submarines will be relocated to Scotland

22-03-2017 Lewis Elliott, Marit de Vries, Susanne Wuijts and Liesbet Dirven-van Breemen

Annex V BlueHealth City Profile Tallinn (workshop material)

City profile TALLINN

Demography

- 413,782 inhabitants in 2015 (30% of Estonia's population).
- 52% Estonians, 38% Russians, 10% others
- Population above 65 years will increase to 20% by 2030 (from 17% in 2011).
- Gross wages of the residents of Tallinn are higher than the Estonian average. Leads to domestic in-migration.
- Ethnic-cultural diversity of the city and respective promotion and consumption options.

Fig. Population pyramid Tallinn

Economy

- Tallinn accounts for more than half of Estonia's GDP and employment (OECD, 2019).
- Ferries are the dominant means of transport for visitors to Tallinn (79% vs 5% mean EU28: EuStat2016).
- Competition with higher-salary countries leads to international out-migration of skilled workforce.
- Tallinn is among the rapidly growing GDP/capita metropolitan areas in EU.
- Increase in urban mobility and economic activity causes environmental and social conflicts incl. near waterfront areas

Social-cultural

- Residents of urban fringes also consume the cultural services of the city.
- New residential areas are concentrated near the city limits and in close proximity to the coastal area.
- Ageing of population > increased demand for social services.

Fig. Most Tallinners assess their health as (very) good.

Technology

- Priority development clusters are high-tech manufacturing, ICT, maritime and logistics, creative industries and biotechnology.
- Perspective on Tallinn-Helsinki international undersea tunnel.
- Increased availability of drinking water dependent on upgrading processing facilities and technologies.

Ecology & Climate

- 85% of the city water supply is taken from Lake Ülemiste, eutrophication raises purification costs.
- Urban waterbodies are in poor state; several watercourses in Tallinn have been diverted into pipes.
- Many unused and unplugged bore wells are a threat to water contamination.
- Environmental risks related to sea transport – fuel, oil, rubbish.
- 1995-2014 Hydrocarbons, suspended solids, BOD, tot N, tot P are trending downwards, but pH upwards, in Tallinn area storm water flows in the recent decades (Maharjan ea 2016).

Fig. Climate Graph, Tallinn, Estonia

Political-Institutional

- Tallinn Development Plan includes environmental targets + Environmental Strategy 2030.
- Lack of a rain water strategy for Tallinn
- Increase in house prices in coastal areas due to gentrification.
- Policy and investment priority to boost ICT infrastructure and increase digital literacy.

Fig. Social benefits independent on family income considerably increased.

16-04-2015, Liesbet Dirven -van Breemen, Mart Kiviik and Marit de Vries

Annex VI BlueHealth City Profile Thessaloniki (workshop material)

City profile THESSALONIKI

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